

AN AMERICAN SCIENTIFIC JOURNAL

Zien Journal

of

Social Sciences and Humanities

VOLUME 27, DECEMBER-2023

Articles

1. **Analysis Of Criminal And Criminal-Procedural Legislation Of Foreign Countries Regulating Proceedings Up To Trial For Crimes Of Violation Of Statute Rules Of Relationships Between Non Subordinate Military Servants**

1-5 Alautdinov Dilmurad Alautdin Ogli

2. **Historical Aspects Of The Development Of International Relations In Uzbekistan**

10-13 Oydinova Bureau

3. **On The Coins of The Pre-Islamic Fergana Valley**

6-9 Nurbek Allabergenov

4. **The effect of improving the quality of products in livestock breeding by innovative methods**

14-17 Bahodirjon Nosirov, Elyorbek Nurmatov

5. **Improving quality and efficiency on the basis of production resources in cattle breeding**

18-21 Bahodirjon Nosirov, Elyorbek Nurmatov

6. **Services Of A. Orinboev In Cataloging Works**

22-25 Burkhanov Ilyaskhan Mukhiddinovich, Burkhanov Ilyaskhan Mukhiddinovich

7. **The Essence Of Michelle Montin's Philosophical Views**

26-28 Kurbonov Umidjon Egamberdiyevich

8. **The Attractiveness Of Muhammad Yusuf's Poetry**

29-31 Ma'rifatov Khursandbek

9. **Study Of Current Problems And Solutions Of Uzbek Theater Art**

32-35 Nurpo'latova Ozoda Hasan qizi

Analysis Of Criminal And Criminal-Procedural Legislation Of Foreign Countries Regulating Proceedings Up To Trial For Crimes Of Violation Of Statute Rules Of Relationships Between Non Subordinate Military Servants

Alautdinov Dilmurad Alautdin Ogli

Deputy head of the Academy of the Ministry of Internal Affairs, docent

Annotation: Through this article, you can learn about the analysis and specifics of the norms that regulate the conduct of proceedings before the court in connection with the crime of violation of the charter provisions regarding the interaction between military personnel who are not subordinate to each other in the criminal and criminal-procedural legislation of foreign countries. The analysis of the norms regulating the conduct of proceedings before the court regarding the crime of violation of the charter provisions regarding the mutual relations between military personnel who are not subordinate to each other in the criminal and criminal-procedural legislation of foreign countries is aimed at improving the criminal legislation.

Key words: non-subordinate serviceman, statutory provisions, objective party, routine humiliation, military surveillance, command surveillance.

Introduction

The reforms implemented in all spheres in our country are, first of all, ensuring the rights and freedoms of citizens enshrined in the Constitution and laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan, a democratic legal state based on our national values and aimed at establishing a free civil society. From this point of view, the reforms carried out in our country created the need to form a new legal basis in the life of the state and society, to ensure the rights and liberties of citizens and consistent compliance with the law.

At this point, it should be noted that among the fundamental reforms being carried out in our country, criminal legislation was also reformed. As the first among the countries of the Commonwealth of Independent States, at the 16th session of the Supreme Council of the Republic of Uzbekistan on September 22, 1994, the Criminal and Criminal Procedure Codes of the Republic of Uzbekistan were adopted and entered into legal force on April 1, 1995.

The above-mentioned norms regulating the proceedings before the court regarding the violation of the charter provisions regarding the mutual relations between non-subordinate military personnel have their own characteristics in the criminal and criminal-procedural legislation of foreign countries.

When analyzing the norms of criminal and criminal procedural legislation of the Central Asian republics, the punishment measures applied to military personnel, investigative bodies, application of precautionary measures and other procedural measures do not differ much from the legislation of our country.

Discussion And Results

The advanced criminal procedural practice of the Republic of Kazakhstan has been bearing fruit for many years. The separate procedure for handling crimes committed by military personnel is defined in the Criminal Procedure Code of the Republic of Kazakhstan, which is fundamentally different from that of other countries. In contrast to the separate proceedings established in the JPK of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the proceedings in the JPK of the Republic of Kazakhstan on military crimes, on crimes against women, on crimes committed by recidivist criminals and on appeals are conducted separately. According to Article 323 of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Kazakhstan, proceedings on crimes committed by military personnel are conducted by military prosecutors and military police bodies. In addition, among the preventive measures applied to servicemen who have committed a crime in Kazakhstan, there is a preventive measure of command surveillance, in which servicemen serve on the basis of surveillance in a separate order. In the event that the serviceman's term of service has expired, the command surveillance will be changed to a more severe prison

measure if the serviceman does not violate the requirements of the preventive measure by the prosecutor conducting the investigation. This practice, i.e. applying more severe precautions to military personnel, had a positive effect on the crime rates of this group.

Among the countries of Central Asia, the military criminal legislation of Uzbekistan is closer to the military criminal legislation of the Republic of Kazakhstan. The structural structure of Article 440 of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Kazakhstan is similar to Article 285 of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan. However, normative decision No. 6 of the Supreme Court of the Republic of Kazakhstan dated October 28, 2005 "On judicial practice on military crimes" dated September 15, 2000 of the Plenum of the Supreme Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On judicial practice on hearing cases related to crimes against the order of military service" dated September 15, 2000 It is quite different from decision No. 23. Because, in the criminal legislation of other countries, the importance of qualification through non-repetitive aspects, that is, repeated crimes of military personnel, time of military service, and other norms is defined. In the decision of the Plenum of the Supreme Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On judicial practice regarding the consideration of cases related to crimes against the order of military service" dated September 15, 2000 No. 23, from when a military serviceman can become the subject of this crime, from when his military service ends, this crime is repeated in the case of the qualification process, what circumstances should be taken into account, what are the aggravating and mitigating circumstances, and many other terms and concepts are not defined, so there is a misunderstanding and a legal gap in these cases. Bridging these gaps is the main task before us.

Crime of the Republics of Turkmenistan and Tajikistan

and any serviceman who commits a crime under criminal procedure law shall be dismissed from military service. Tajik military legislation pays particular attention to the issue of compensation for material damage. If a military serviceman is discharged from military service as a result of committing a crime, all expenses incurred are military service covered by tchi. In this country, crimes of violating the provisions of the charter regarding mutual relations between military personnel who are not subordinate to each other are committed in a large number, but procedurally, they are not considered in a separate order. The investigation of the crime under investigation is carried out by the prosecutor's office and, although the law provides for precautionary measures against military personnel, command surveillance is rarely used. The reason for this is determined by the existence of the order of dismissal from military service of military personnel who have committed a crime.

The criminal and criminal-procedural legislation of the Russian Federation is of particular importance among the foreign experiences regarding the crime studied within the framework of the research. Punishment measures, terms of punishment, actions towards the objectively selected objective have their own characteristics. Perfection of this crime norm can be attributed to the fact that this crime is often committed in Tsarist Russia, the USSR, and even today in Russia, as well as the fact that the crime norm was developed based on many years of practical experience.

The investigation is conducted by military district attorneys and, as a precaution, command surveillance is used in almost all cases.

According to Article 30 of the Criminal Procedure Code of Russia, the issue of general or separate prosecution of crimes committed by military servicemen or citizens undergoing military training is decided by the decision of the judge of the military district court based on the presentation of the district prosecutor.

The Criminal Procedure Code of Russia does not have separate norms for proceedings in a separate order, and no other procedure for proceedings in a separate order is defined. Only through some norms, he gave the discretion of the court to consider the case in a separate order.

Russian scientist A. Mikhalaev emphasized that the rate of committing military crimes in Russia is higher than in other countries, analyzed in his scientific work the need to develop a separate procedure for handling the cases of military servicemen, and added a separate rule on the procedure for handling the cases of military personnel to the Criminal Procedure Code of Russia. emphasized.

Russian scientist E. Sachenov agrees with the opinion of A. Mikhalaev and emphasizes that it is necessary to conduct the case separately not only in relation to military crimes, but in all other criminal cases. According to A. Sachenov, considering the case in a separate order creates a basis for legal, fair and high-

quality management. In our opinion, these opinions are correct, and it is necessary to develop specific criteria for handling the case in a separate order and include it in the criminal procedural code.

In the criminal-procedural codes of Azerbaijan, Belarus and a number of other countries, proceedings on crimes committed by military personnel are carried out in a general manner, there are no specific criteria for a separate procedure, and the proceedings on these crimes are conducted by military police bodies and general supervision is carried out by prosecutors. is increased. The precautions applied to military personnel in these countries differ from the laws of other countries. The Code of Criminal Procedure of Azerbaijan has a norm of preventive measures applied to military personnel, which stipulates the use of preventive measures of military guarantee, military surveillance, military team control, and commander's surveillance. Belarusian criminal-procedural legislation widely uses this practice when the above norm is not met.

In the countries of Germany, Sweden, and Turkey, the regulation of this crime, unlike other countries, is not regulated by the criminal and criminal-procedural codes, but by the "War Crimes" code. This code includes all crimes committed by military personnel and the process of procedural regulation of these crimes. This, in turn, means that crimes of this category are treated in a separate order, and that special skills are required in the treatment of these types of crimes. As advanced experience of these countries, not only the code mentioned above, but also the experiences of military lawyers, which are not found in many countries, have their own characteristics. Military lawyers serve as the main factor in the legality and fair determination of responsibility in the criminal proceedings for violation of the statutory provisions regarding the interaction between military personnel who are not subordinate to each other. According to the Turkish Code of Military Crimes, a special procedure for compensation of damages caused as a result of the crime is established, and this experience is also of special importance. Turkey is based on the principle of severity in the application of punishment and precautionary measures to military personnel. Command surveillance used as a precautionary measure is subject to surveillance and control separately, as well as the attachment of weapons to this serviceman, It is strictly forbidden to carry out work and other important tasks.

In the Japanese state, unlike the historical stage of development, it is characterized by the abandonment of measures of responsibility for this crime. Two years after World War II, a new Japanese constitution came into force, prohibiting the country from having an army through constitutional norms. Also, Japan was denied the right to use military force as a means of resolving international conflicts. However, in 1991-1992, Japan felt the need for self-defense, conscripts were drafted into the army, and the Ministry of Defense was established in 2007. According to the Japanese Criminal Code, military personnel are only liable if they cause material damage to the army. All other illegal actions will be considered in general. In these cases, the regulation of procedural processes is regulated not by codes, but by separate laws. For example, the law "Criminal proceedings against Japanese military personnel" regulates the process of procedurally handling of crimes committed by military personnel. War crimes investigations are carried out by police investigators. Imprisonment as a precautionary measure under the above Act is an effective punishment.

According to the criminal procedure law of the USA, crimes of military servicemen not arising from their official duties (causing physical injuries, rough treatment, humiliation, slander, insults, etc.) are considered in a general manner. Crimes resulting from the performance of duty (destruction of military property, disobedience of command, robbery of military property, etc.) are investigated by military prosecutors with special knowledge. Although there are many cases of illegal behavior of military personnel among themselves, these actions do not qualify as war crimes. In the US, there is no special protective order against military personnel, but collateral protection is often used in many cases. Some states of the USA (Florida, Texas, Guam, Virginia, Colorado) have separate laws that regulate the qualification and procedural processes of crimes committed by military personnel. This country also has an institute of military lawyers, which performs the task of defending military personnel at any stage of criminal proceedings.

In China, administrative and criminal cases are not separated from each other. Military crimes, like other crimes, are tried by regional prefects' courts and heads of district military departments. Between 1986 and 1999, as war crimes increased, so did the use of the death penalty for these crimes. According to the principle of "joint responsibility" in Chinese law, not only the participants but also their superiors are sentenced to death for illegal actions of military personnel against each other. Through such harsh punishments, the scale of war crimes in China has decreased dramatically. In China, some types of crimes (recidivist crimes, crimes endangering the peace, crimes causing the death of people, crimes committed by

minors) as well as crimes committed by military personnel are investigated by the investigators of the police investigation group established under the higher district courts. Military lawyers are recruited on behalf of military servicemen. Precautionary detention is used a lot.

India is one of the countries with the largest and most powerful army in the world. Accordingly, many illegal acts are committed among the servicemen of this army. The Code of Offenses and Criminal Procedure of India lays down the procedure for dealing with crimes committed by military personnel. According to it, if illegal actions are committed between military personnel who are not subordinate to each other, they will be subjected to a separate prison measure and kept separately. India

one of the specific features of the criminal procedural law is that in certain types of criminal cases, the proceedings against the victim and the accused are conducted separately, that is, not by one police investigator, but separate investigators are involved to investigate the participants of each crime. Although special knowledge is not required for police investigators, investigative actions and court costs are collected from both sides. In India, depending on the type of crime, the procedural terms of conducting criminal proceedings are determined, and the longest period, i.e. from one to five years, is conducted in the case of military personnel.

The number of war crimes in Saudi Arabia, UAE and Yemen has increased dramatically recently. Following the military unrest in Yemen alone

112 thousand people died. In these countries, responsibility for crimes is regulated on the basis of religious norms. The honor and dignity of military personnel is at the state level is protected. The investigation is carried out by individual investigators. According to the criminal law of these countries, if a military serviceman commits an act that causes the death of his partner due to his actions against the king during military service, he is sentenced to death. Investigators investigating war crimes are also guided by applicable law and religious norms. At the request of the victim, as well as religious lawyers, civil lawyers have the right to participate in the case. As a precaution, military community control is often used.

In Iraq and Syria, the number of war crimes is also increasing, despite the fact that the unrest has escalated. The atmosphere among military personnel is not good. According to statistics, more than 20 military personnel shoot each other in one day in Syria and Iraq. The issue of responsibility of the perpetrators of these actions is not specified in the legal documents. According to scientists, one of the main reasons for the weakening of these countries is the military

they are rude to each other. The non-existence of an investigation body for military crimes is explained by the fact that the act is not defined as a crime. In these countries, without dividing crimes into types, any separate category of crimes are carried out by the same body and in the same order. Procedural coercive measures and precautionary measures applied to other persons are also applied to military personnel.

Another country where wars are raging is Ukraine. More than 21,000 "war crimes" were committed in Ukraine during 6 months of 2022. Today's state of conflicting relations of the military to each other has increased 150 times compared to the peacetime. According to the information of the Ministry of Defense of Ukraine, the responsibility for the actions of military personnel against the king, if it is committed during the war, i.e. in an emergency, the punishment will be more severe than prescribed by the law. Law "On Criminal Liability of Military Servicemen of Ukraine" and the Criminal Code of Ukraine

According to Article 406, more than 20 actions contrary to the law were evaluated as rude actions of military personnel against each other, and military prosecutors conducted investigations. According to unofficial data, because of the impossibility of applying precautionary measures to military personnel for committing crimes, the indicators of committing military crimes are increasing and criminals are being deported to the "hotbeds of war".

Belgium and Moldova also have measures of responsibility for this crime, which are procedurally regulated. Criminal proceedings are carried out by the military police and military prosecutor's offices. In these countries, a military serviceman (accused) who has committed a crime has the right to choose a preventive measure, and they choose preventive measures with the same effect. The military police and military prosecutor's office may impose other restrictions on a military serviceman who has committed a crime than those specified in the selected precautionary measure (attachment of arms, enlistment, participation in military operations).

Conclusion

By applying the experiences of foreign countries to our national military-criminal law, we can create a more perfect criminal-procedural law. Studying the legislation of developed countries creates conditions for us to eliminate mistakes and shortcomings in the development of our legislation, and to give a legal correct assessment to legal conflicts.

Based on the above-mentioned advanced foreign experiences, it is necessary to increase the types of precautionary measures applied to military personnel, take special control of military personnel under command surveillance, and revise the restrictions imposed on them. In addition, the institute of military lawyers should be introduced in our country. The experiences of developed countries show that the participation of military lawyers has positive results. The main task before us is to develop separate forms of the procedure for crimes committed by military personnel based on foreign experiences. The military serviceman's choice of the limitations of precautionary measures is a means of ensuring human rights.

List Of References Used

1. N. Salaev. Some problems in determining the objective signs of the crime of violation of the provisions of the charter on the relationship between military personnel who are not subordinate to each other and their solution. Inlibrary analysis of the legislation of Uzbekistan 2010 -B 44-46.
2. Under the editorship of A. Madvaliev. - Tashkent: "National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan" State Scientific Publishing House, 2008. - B. 641-642
3. Commentary on the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Rustamboev. Tashkent. Justice 2016. - [electronic resource]. Date of application: 08.11.2022. Access path: https://drive.google.com/file/d/1ctKcLoMP8UaC5BgGscM_S-AI0i8fjYlh/view
4. An explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language. 5 volumes. T.5. / under the editorship of A. Madvaliev. - Tashkent: "National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan" State Scientific Publishing House, 2008.
5. The Convention against Torture and Other Cruel, Inhuman or Degrading Treatment or Punishment of December 10, 1984. // Saidov A.Kh. International law on human rights: Textbook. - Tashkent: Konsauditinform-Nashr, 2006. -B. 318-335.
6. Journalism in conflict situations. Electronic study guide. Date of application: 21.09.2023. Access: https://nargis.uz/wp-content/uploads/2019/10/09.04.2019_1_journalism_in_conflict_situations.pdf
7. Decision No. 23 of September 15, 2000 of the Plenum of the Supreme Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the judicial practice of hearing cases related to crimes against the order of military service".
8. Mirzaev T.Q. Qabulov R. Crimes against the order of military service: Instructional manual. - Tashkent: Talqin, 2005. - B. 24.
9. Salaev N.S. Violation of the statutory provisions on mutual relations between military personnel who are not subordinate to each other (criminal-legal and criminological aspects). Law. science. name science narrow written to receive. diss... - Tashkent: TDYuI, 2012. - B. 71.
10. Sh.M. Gurbanov, Criminal-legal nature of violation of the charter provisions on mutual relations of military personnel in the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Analysis of the legislation of Uzbekistan. Tashkent-2018, No. 2.

On The Coins of The Pre-Islamic Fergana Valley

Nurbek Allabergenov, 1st year doctoral student
of the National Archeological Center of the
Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan

Abstract. From ancient times to the present, various civilizations and cultures have existed in the territory of Central Asia. In this article, we have thoroughly analyzed the early medieval numismatic materials of the Ferghana Valley region, one of the oldest regions of Central Asia, compared the coins found during excavations in archaeological monuments, and made general conclusions. O.I.Smirnova, L.S.Baratova, E.Rtveladze, G.Babayarov carried out extensive works on the numismatics of this region, and we analyzed the data in their scientific works. We can say that the coins found in Fergana region, like the coins found in other historical regions of our country, give us very clear and important information about the period of their minting

Keywords: Ferghana, Choch, Isfijab, Khagan, numismatic materials, Turkic Khaganate, early Middle Ages, Kuva

Enter. In the early Middle Ages, the Fergana Valley consisted of several large and small administrations - estates, sometimes their number reached up to 6. Although pre-Islamic Chinese and Arab-Persian sources mention a number of political associations in the Ferghana valley, they are not mentioned by name, so it is not possible to fully determine which areas of the valley these political associations encompassed and which dynasties ruled them. Even numismatic materials cannot help enough in this matter.

In this matter, when we get acquainted with the political-administrative structure and ruling dynasties of Chach, Ustrushana and Isfijab (Sayram) regions neighboring or somewhat close to the Ferghana valley in the early Middle Ages, it is noticeable that a somewhat different situation prevailed. In particular, it is known that coins were issued by dynasties such as Chach tegins, Chach tuduns, Chach rulers [Baratova L.S. 2007. – B.43-49] Each of Ustrushana and Isfijab principalities was basically ruled by one dynasty, and it is understood that the political-administrative aspect in them was somewhat different from that of Choch.

Methodology. In contrast to the large settled principalities of Central Asia, such as Choch and Sugd, Tokhoristan, the types, weight, geography of distribution of Ferghana Valley coins and archaeological monuments where coins were found are relatively few. Researchers mainly explain this situation as follows [Babayarov G. 2023. – B. 97-118]:

- 1) in the early Middle Ages, the coin-money system was relatively poorly developed in the Ferghana valley, and the first tradition of coin minting here began during the period of the Turkic khaganate;
- 2) in most of the archaeological sites in the valley, the cultural layers belonging to the early Middle Ages have not been sufficiently excavated. Therefore, the pre-Islamic Ferghana coins are not well known to the world of science.

Coins belonging to the pre-Islamic period found by chance from other regions of Central Asia, especially from regions such as Tashkent, Samarkand, Bukhara, etc., are quite large. However, this situation is not so observed in the Ferghana valley. This strengthens the view that the use of coins in the Ferghana valley in the early Middle Ages was somewhat slower than in other regions.

Table 1. Ferghana coins of the early Middle Ages (Baratova L.S. 2007. – B.43-49; Babayarov G. 2007. – B.151-156) .

N o	Titles on coins	Coin pictures	Mintage and commemoration	Published research
--------	-----------------	---------------	---------------------------------	-----------------------

1	1. <i>qǧn (Qaǧan)</i> " khagan " and <i>knm?</i> "ruler" (obverse) <i>[x'j'nc pny?]</i> "Khagan's coin?" (reverse) 2. <i>[q]ǧn (Qaǧan)</i> "Khagan" and <i>knm?</i> (obverse), <i>[cp]yw? x'[j'n]</i> "Djabgu-khagan?" (reverse)		VII century. Kuva	Babayarov 2004 : 32, Babayarov 2023: 98-99 ; Baratova 2007: 44
2	<i>x'j'n</i> "khagan" (obverse) , the reverse side is without writing (reverse)		VII - VIII centuries .Kuva, Kyzil-tepa (Osh) and others.	Smirnova 1981: 338-339, No. 1435, Babayarov 2023: 99-100
3	<i>x'j'n</i> "Khagan" (obverse), <i>βryn</i> "Fergana" (reverse)		VII - VIII centuries .Kuva, Kizil-tepa (Osh) and others.	Smirnova 1981 : 340, No. 1441 ; Babayarov 2023: 100-101
4	<i>prn</i> " kut " (obverse) , <i>pny</i> "coin" (reverse)		VII - VIII centuries. Kuva	Baratova 2007: 43-49; Babayar 2007: 151-156

Analysis and results. Some researchers, in particular O.I. Smirnova, L.S. The Baratovas believe that other coins than those listed in this table were minted in the Fergana Valley. They are as follows: 1) coins with the image of the ruler and the queen on the right surface, and the stamp on the reverse side and the Sugdian inscription around it; 2) coins with the image of the ruler facing straight on the right surface, and the stamp on the reverse side and the words «farn bagi... » in Sugdian script next to it; 3) coins with the words «Alp-khagan tutuq» in Sugdian writing on the right surface, with no writing on the reverse surface, imitation of Chinese coins with a square hole in the middle.

In fact, some of these coins belong to Sugd and Otrar rule in the following table:

Table 2. Coins indicated as belonging to the reign of Ferghana, but in recent years have been identified as belonging to other reigns

No	Titles on coins	Coin pictures	Mintage and commemoration	Published research
1	<i>MR'Y βcs' j'twnh</i> "ruler ... wife" (O.I. Smirnova); <i>MR'Y pny nn x'twnh</i> "Ruler Nana-Khatun coin" or "Ruler (and) Nana-Khotun coin"		VII - VIII centuries . _ Samarkand, Fergana, Tashkent vil.	Smirnova 1981: 359; Babayarov 2021: 96 , 176; Babayarov, Kubatin

				2013: 95-107
2	<i>prn βγγ...</i> "Divine kut..." (O.I. Smirnova); <i>prn βγγ pny</i> "Divine kut (owner)" (G'. Babayarov)		VII - VIII centuries . _ Fergana Valley, Panjikent, Samarkand region	Smirnova 1981: 7, 25, 54; Babayarov 2023: 65-76
3	<i>lpw? γ'γ'n twtwγ</i> "Alp-khagan tutuq"		VII - VIII centuries . _ Ferghana Valley, Varakhsha, Otrar, Sayram (Gen. Kazakhstan)	Smirnova 1981: 56-57; Babayarov, Kubatin 2014: 183-194; Baytanaev et al. 2020 : 134-135, 200, 203

The coins listed in this table were issued at the time of Although included by O.I. Smirnova in the «Group of Ferghana coins», the researcher did not lose sight of the possibility that they belonged to other rulers [Smirnova. 1981 – B.58]. However, a number of researchers who conducted research after that did not reach a decision on whether these coins belong to the Ferghana Valley or vice versa. In particular, L.S. Baratova connects the coins with the title «Alp-khagan tutuq» with the Fergana valley [Baratova L.S. 2007. – B.45], G. Babayarov and A. Kubatins proved that they belong to the Otrar rulership [Babayarov G. 2014. – B.183-194]. Pre-Islamic coins of Ferghana mostly bear the title «khagan», which was used by the supreme rulers of the Turkic khaganate at that time. The appearance of this title on coins of Ferghana is considered to have been minted directly or indirectly in connection with the Turkic khaganate [Babayarov G. 2014. – B.70-75]. In due time O.I. Smirnova, L.S. The Baratovas included these coins in the «group of ancient Turkic coins of Central Asia», but left open the question of which Turkic dynasty they were minted by. G. Babayarov believes that Ferghana coins with the title «khagan» belong to the Ashina dynasty, which ruled the valley in the 7th-8th centuries. According to him, the Ashina dynasty, which became the leading dynasty in the Ferghana Valley in the second quarter of the 7th century, dates back to the Western Turkic Khaganate, and the representatives of this dynasty ruled until the first quarter of the 9th century. Their rule in the valley was ended in 810 by the Arab viceroys, one of the founders of the Samanid dynasty, Ahmad ibn Asad [Babayarov G. 2023. – B.42]. The iconography on the coins of the Ferghana Valley - the image of the ruler, the shape of the stamp, the title, etc., is very close to the coins of the West Turkic Khaganate minted in the Choch oasis at the end of the 6th - beginning of the 7th century. This further strengthens the view that Ferghana was ruled by representatives of the Ashina dynasty at that time. It is known that in the 630s, after one of the Western Turkic khagans killed the local ruler of Ferghana named Kibi, the administration of the valley was transferred to the representatives of the Ashina dynasty (Bichurin N.Y.1950. – B.284).

Summary.In short, in the early Middle Ages, more precisely, in the 6th - 8th centuries, the Ferghana Valley was a separate oasis under the rule of the Turkic Khaganate, and the main power here belonged to the representatives of the Ashina dynasty. Other dynasties in the valley were subordinate to this house and had some freedom in their internal administration. Apparently, they did not have the right to mint their own coins. A small number of coins found in the remains of the old city of the Fergana valley belong to the Ashina dynasty, and are confirmed by the title «khagan» typical of the khaganate. Apparently, the representatives of this dynasty minted coins in the name of Western Turkic khagans. On the other hand, as a branch of the khaganate, it is hypothesized that the representatives of the Ferghana Ashina dynasty used this title while issuing their coins.

Used literature

1. Бабаяров Г. Монеты Отрара с изображением парного портрета // Тарихий манбашунослик тарихнавислик тарих тадқиқоти методлари ва методологиясининг долзарб масалалари мавзуидаги Республика VI илмий-назарий конференциясининг материаллари. – Тошкент: 2014.
2. Бабаяров Г., Кубатин А. К вопросу о некоторых доисламских монетах Отрара // Проблемы изучения нематериального культурного наследия народов Казахстана и Центральной Азии: топонимика, эпиграфика, искусство. Сб. мат-лов межд.науч. конф. – Алматы: Издательство EVO PRESS, 2014. – С.183-194.
3. Бабаяров Г. Древнетюркские монеты Чачского оазиса (VI–VIII вв.). – Ташкент: 2007. – С.183-194.
4. Бабаяров Г. Фарбий турк хоқонлиги: тарихи ва танга-пул тизими. – Ташкент: 2021.
5. Байтанаев Б.А., Петров П.Н., Брагин А.О. Денежное обращение в Южном Казахстане в III – XV вв. Книга I. – Алматы: 2020.
6. Баратова Л.С. Некоторые аспекты товарно-денежных отношений Ферганы в древности и раннем средневековье // Марғилон шаҳрининг жаҳон цивилизацияси тарихидаги ўрни. Марғилон шаҳрининг 2000 йиллик юбилейига бағишланган ҳақларо илмий конференция материаллари. – Тошкент – Марғилон: Фан, 2007.
7. Бернштам А.Н. Древняя Фергана (Научно-популярный очерк). –Ташкент: 1951.
8. Бичурин Н.Я. (Иакинф). Собрание сведений о народах обитавших в Средней Азии в древние времена. – М.: 1950.
9. Бобоёров Ғ. Чоч тарихидан лавҳалар [Илк ўрта асрлар]. – Тошкент: 2011.
10. Бобоёров Ғ. Фарбий Турк хоқонлиги Ашина сулоласининг Фарғонадаги тармоғи тарихига доир // O‘zbekiston tarixi. – Тошкент: 2019. № 3.

Historical Aspects Of The Development Of International Relations In Uzbekistan

Oydinova Bureau

"Alfraganus University" Non-Profit Higher Education
Organization Teacher

Abstract. This article highlights the influence of inter-ethnic relations, which have historically been formed on the territory of Uzbekistan, on national culture. Also, the specific features of inter-ethnic relations are revealed. At the same time, the traditions of tolerance and their specific formation factors, which are the basis for the formation of national cultural processes in the territory of Uzbekistan, have been scientifically analyzed.

Key words: creative activity, traditions of tolerance, «Avesta», semi-nomadic Uzbeks, Uzbek, interethnic relations, tolerance.

LOG IN. (Matthew 24:14; 28:19, 20) Today, there is a tradition of interethnic harmony in the world based on the close relationship between people of all ethnic groups. (Matthew 24:14; 28:19, 20) Jehovah's Witnesses would be pleased to discuss these answers with you. These cultures and traditions form the cornerstone of the first system of civilization. Traditions of tolerance played a major role in dealings with neighbors. Ancient written sources note that these tribes, considered our ancestors, formed large associations. According to these sources, during the seventh and sixth centuries B.C.E., slaughterers, Baqtrians, and Horazmi lived in the subsistence farming valleys of Uzbekistan, and the high urban culture they created had a strong foundation and were able to compete with the ancient Oriental city. They lived in the mountains, deserts and deserts of Central Asia and Kazakhstan, as well as the massacres, mainly livestock, and developed cultural and economic relations with the grassy population.

Various peoples who lived in the first half of the first millennium B.C.E. spoke ancient Eastern Ethiopian languages and languages, and their ethnicity and languages were close to one another. Therefore, the Sons, the Baqtrians, the Chaldeans, the Saxons, and the Massacres were brothers and sisters, and they understood each other well. (Matthew 24:14; 28:19, 20) In particular, the material and spiritual culture of farmers and grassy tribes, as well as the farming and culture of the city, were similar.

The roots of many nations and polygamy date back to ancient times. The holy books and grandeurs of the Zardohis, such as "Ar·ta·xerx'es," ancient Iran, Greece, China, Roman sources, and other written monuments, have provided information about the country's grassy and nomadic population to our day. Over the centuries, various invaders: Alexander II of Macedonia, the Arabian Empire, Chihuahua, and the Russian Empire marched into our country for looting and colonial purposes. During the reign of Emperor Tiberius, representatives of other peoples began to emigrate there. The fortress houses members of the Holy Scriptures—With References. Along with them, new language, religion, and cultural values came here. Each of the peoples brought its own culture here. The fact that our country is located on the Great Silk Road played a major role in these processes. Stretching thousands of miles, the road has served as a bridge connecting the West and the East for centuries. It was not only a trade route but also a means of active cultural cooperation and cooperation between nations and religions.

Methodology. The region consisted mostly of high, sparsely wooded tablelands through by deep ravines. The hospitality and open volunteering of the inhabitants of the tube place played a major role in the settling of the peoples who came here. Thus, over a long period of historical history, the diverse ethnicity of the people of Uzbekistan has been formed, resulting in the formation of nations by the early 20th century, as well as the formation of different ethnic groups on the basis of migration. "Since the 17th century, the main people between the two rivers have been called Uzbeks. In the 18th century, changes took place in the location of

almost all nations in the region, and the process of mass migration took place. (Usmanov Q., Sodiqov M., Burhanova S. 1993. – B. 36-45).

The region consisted mostly of high, sparsely silvery pitched into the region. Despite migration in the late 19th century, the non-substantial population was very small here. In 1884, there were 6,1,000 inhabitants of the province. The largest ethnic group was the Turks, with a population of 475.6,000. «Nomadic and semi-nomadic Uzbeks (5.7 thousand), nomadic kittens (5.6 thousand), Turks (5.7 thousand) built (1.4 thousand), faces (0.3 thousand) were close to them in language. All of these ethnic groups later joined together to be called Uzbeks, making up 1,000 people and 69% of the total population. Next, there were 104.1,000 kyrgyzs (14.5%), and in the third place were 43.2,000 Tajiks (6.0%)." (Rakhmatillaev, Kh. 1988. – B. 45).

Located between the subsistence farming districts of the Fergana Valley, Samarkand and Tashkent region, Mirzachoel was another unique place. At the end of the 19th century, there were 175,000 inhabitants. The lifestyle of many of them was semi-nomadic. "There were 145,000 Uzbeks among the semi-nomadic population, 18,000 among the grassy population, 5,000 inhabitants, and 3.5,000 Russians. The Kazakhs were mainly part of the nomadic population. (Aminor 1969. - 45-47) Jehovah's Witnesses would be pleased to answers with you.

The ethnicity of several cities was very diverse. This was especially noticeable in the cities built after the invasion of the Russian Empire. If "In Margillon, Anchorage, Mogadishu, and Namangan, Uzbeks accounted for 97.6%, while New Margillon was the population of present-day Fargo: Russians 42.9%, Uzbeks 29.2%, Ukrainians 8.1%, Poles, Jews, mainly Jews of Bucharest - 2.0%, Germans – 1.7%, Tatars – 1.6%, Kyrgyzs-0.9%, Armenians – 0.5%, Chinese – 0.3%, Uighurs – 0.2%, etc." —Raathilleew, 1988. – 67. The situation in the main city of Tashkent was similar. Its 155673 inhabitants called 43 languages their native language. Alongside large groups of Turkish-speaking groups, the city considered Greek, English, Italian, and other languages to be native. So in addition to the inexact population, there were groups of representatives of other nations living in present-day Uzbekistan.

The period from July 1881 to June 1886 can be considered a new phase of the process of moving to the general government of Burma because there are major discrepancies between objective socio-economic situations in Burma and the rules of relocation in 1881 and 1886. "It is estimated that from 1889 to 1891, 28911 families or more than 100,000 people moved to Burma."—Coffin A. 1903. - B. 20. In the years that followed, crop yields occurred in the Volga and a number of other grainy regions of Russia, and the number of displaced people increased as the famine began. As a result, by 1892, after the land of the inhabitants of the area in the province of Syrdarya was quickly transported to displaced people, there were almost no vacant lands left. "According to these rules, the move of rascals was allowed not only to russians who worship the Orthodox church but also to the Russians with the approval of the Ministry of Internal Affairs. (Gonzbing A.I. – M.: 1998. – B. 35) Jehovah's Witnesses would be pleased to answers with you.

The last decade of the 20th century is characterized by a period of dramatic changes in the history of our country in needy, political, and international development. On August 31, 1991, when Uzbekistan declared its independence, a number of important political documents were adopted to preserve political independence and meet its capabilities more quickly and courageously. A key factor in this was that independence should have been politically understood and felt first and foremost by the people. In the most difficult period of establishing our own national sovereignty, our society has been able to reliably respond to various factors and threats in terms of the political, religious, ethnic and other characteristics that destabilize it.

Analysis And Results. Today, citizens of more than 136 different ethnic groups live a peaceful and prosperous life in the country, equalizing their rights and freedoms. They are engaged in creative and creative work on the road to bringing Uzbekistan to the ranks of developed countries in the future. It is important to acknowledge that our country has opened the door to a wide range of opportunities to redesign the language, cultural achievements, and values of each nation. This is a guarantee of the sustainable development of our country. In a speech to the Supreme Court, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan said: "It is our main goal that everyone living in our country will live a free and wealthy life, regardless of their nationality, language, or religion."—Sh.M. Abdurahman. December 28, 2018. the emphasis is placed on ensuring interethnic harmony. The legal basis for interethnic relations has been established to meet the rights and needs of every citizen living in the country for his or her national prosperity. To assist individuals desiring to benefit

the worldwide work of Jehovah's Witnesses through some form of charitable giving, a brochure entitled Charitable Planning to Benefit Kingdom Service Worldwide has been prepared.—Constitution. 2023. – B. 4).

(Matthew 24:14; 28:19, 20) Today, when much attention is paid to ensuring the prosperity of the land and the peace of the land, it is very important for multinationals to pursue national politics on the basis of a proper, clearly intended goal. The development of relations between nations, bringing it into one system, is the most important issue. In multinational countries, any important issues or problems need to arise from their well-being. Such mistakes need to be avoided, drawing conclusions from the consequences of mistakes in the process of interethnic relations.

Like many countries around the world, Uzbekistan is a multinational country, and establishing contact with other nations for our country is one of the most important tasks of our day. In the early days of independence, they began to be overcome over time, commenting separately on mistakes and misconceptions made during the soviet era in interethnic relations. (Matthew 24:14; 28:19, 20) Therefore, there are community organizations and national cultural centers in the country that serve to meet the national cultural needs of certain ethnic groups living there.

Every laws and regulations adopted by President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev have undoubtedly greatly contributed to the development of our country and the development of our country. (Matthew 24:14; 28:19, 20) Jehovah's Witnesses would be pleased to discuss these answers with you. (Sh.M. Abdurahman) Jehovah's Witnesses would be pleased to support more than the address noted above or by telephoning (718) 560 - 7500. May 19, 2017) The decree will also serve to promote international harmony, support their initiatives, strengthen cooperation with foreign countries, and develop relations in any area.

(Matthew 24:14; 28:19, 20) Jehovah's Witnesses would be pleased to discuss these answers with you. Although efforts in this area have not always been successful, in any case the pursuit of cultural relationships, tolerance, and tolerance have remained a constant goal. Uzbekistan belongs to a multinational state. The main ethnic groups, along with Uzbeks, are citizens of more than 136 other ethnic groups with their culture and traditions. (Matthew 24:14; 28:19, 20) In such a situation, I am impressed by the importance of the policy of establishing a multiethnic state and achieving interethnic and interethnic integrity. This policy is aimed at abandoning outdated, unscathed beliefs and integrating the ideas and principles of national independence and spiritual renewal into people's minds.

Conclusion. The unique mentality of the Uzbek people prohibits unity, unity, and cooperation, not division. History tells us that no result in the world can be achieved without accumulating intelligence, energy, time, and opportunities at one point. Unity is a debacle of creativity, and it is a sign of the pursuit of creativity and the composition of the state of public mobilization along the way. The spirituality of each nation, nation, or nation is determined by the degree of perfection of its descendants, how much they know their place in life and how much they feel that they are an integral part of society. It is also reflected in the spirituality, patriotism, peace, self-sacrifice, and hard work of the Uzbek people. (Matthew 24:14; 28:19, 20) In that sense, love and protection of godly devotion play an important role in improving their freedom, freedom, parents, family, brothers, and harmony. On this basis, a wide range of professionals are tasked with improving the training and improving their quality.

Literature List

1. Usmanov Q., Sodiqov M., Burhanova S. History of Uzbekistan. – Tashkent: Fan, 1993. – B. 36-45.
2. Rakhmatillaev Kh. "Dynamics of the Ethnic Structure of the Rural Population of the Fergana Valley / Races and Peoples. Moscow , 1988. №18.
3. Aminov B. Ethnic composition of the population of the Golodnoy degree in the cons of the nineteenth beginning of the twentieth century. – Tashkent: 1969. P. 45-47.
4. Ragmatillaev Kh. Changes in the Ethnic Structure of the Population of the Uzbek Part of the Fergana Valley in the Year of Soviet Power. – Tashkent: 1988. №6.
5. Kaufman A.A. Translation and colony. - T.: SP (b), 1903. - P. 20.
6. Ганзбург А.И. Русское население в Туркестане. – М.: 1998. – Б. 35.

1. Address to the Supreme Court by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoyev, 28.12.2018. <https://president.uz/lists/view/2228>:
2. Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan. – Tashkent: Uzbekistan, 2023. – B.C.E. 4.
3. PF-5046 of May 19, 2017 concerning measures to improve international relations and friendship with foreign countries. <https://lex.uz/docs/3210345>

The effect of improving the quality of products in livestock breeding by innovative methods

Bahodirjon Nosirov, Elyorbek Nurmatov

Andijan Institute of Agriculture and Agrotechnologies, Uzbekistan

Email: bahodirjonn@gmail.com

Resume. The article looks at creative methods to raise product quality and increase agricultural productivity in the cattle industry. Simultaneously, the efficiency indicators for raising animal breeds and raising feed quality in order to produce high-fat milk were examined. Modern assessment techniques and quality performance requirements must be thoroughly understood while creating, delivering, and planning high-quality goods.

Key words: animal husbandry, cattle breeding, intensive method, product quality, feed unit, diet, breeding, selection, milk, economic efficiency, cost, profit, profitability.

Recently, the demand of consumers for quality products is increasing day by day. Because at present, domestic markets of Uzbekistan are in great demand for high-quality products imported from abroad. Our main goal is to increase and fill the domestic market with high-quality products produced by us, and to increase the export potential of Uzbekistan.

By improving the quality of the product, its shelf life will be extended, the cost and labor costs will be reduced, the competitiveness in the world market will increase, the economy of the enterprise will improve and the consumer's demand will be fully satisfied. That is why product quality is an object of planning and management in the economy.

Cattle breeding is an important component of agriculture, supplying almost all dairy products and 60-70% of meat necessary for full nutrition of people.

The rations and type of feeding of agricultural animals it is necessary to take into account the systems of their feeding and the structure of production, the quality of feeds, their cost and the coefficient of beneficial effect.

In the following years, due to the insufficient low level of production of dairy and meat products in our republic, an increasingly large proportion of these foods are brought in at extreme cost.

Livestock sectors produce about 34% of gross agricultural output. More than 90% of it is supplied by small households. So, very few are on farm contributions.

Livestock is one of the important sectors of the economy, which provides the population of the country with important valuable and high-calorie food products. In addition, livestock farms deliver raw materials for the production of products such as light industry, in particular shoes, clothes and furniture, and other things necessary for everyone.

Now let's look at the level of food supply for the population in 2022. Current data shows that Uzbekistan has significant deficiencies in livestock production per capita. Including the provision of milk, beef and poultry is in a state somewhat lower than the World Health Organization's standards. This situation further strengthens the above points on the development of livestock.

The question of improving product quality and increasing its competitiveness is of great importance for the further development of the economy of our republic, including the livestock industry. In the production, supply and planning of high-quality products, it is necessary to be familiar with modern evaluation methods and standards of quality indicators.

In the field of livestock development, work is being carried out to increase the gene pool of livestock breeds and increase meat productivity, and to introduce innovative technologies to expand the fodder base through the use of genetic methods. Innovative development of animal husbandry is first of all directly related to the intensification of production, as a result of the use of improved innovative techniques and technology, as well as new forms of production and labor organization, the effective and full use of available resources ensures an increase in labor productivity.

In the intensive way of increasing the volume of products, attention is mainly focused on increasing

labor productivity, that is, the farm is involved in the production of vitamin-rich fodder, science-technical achievements without changing the number of livestock. As a result, the cost of 1 unit of product decreases, as well as the volume of products increases.

Fodder unit is a unit of measurement that determines the nutritional value of fodder fed to cattle. It is equal to 1 kg of dry oats content of the feed unit. The nutritional value of other forages is compared to this. For example, 1 kg of dry alfalfa is 0.5; barley 1.15; 1 kg of corn is equivalent to 1.4 nutrient units. In cattle, the nutritional value of one feed unit, determined by fat accumulation, is equal to 150 g of internal fat accumulation or 1414 kcal. In addition to the unit of nutrition, digestible protein, calcium, phosphorus, carotene and vitamins are also controlled when evaluating the nutritional value of forage. In practice, special tables are used that indicate the nutritional value of fodder. In the USA, Germany, UK and other countries it is evaluated based on the digestible nutrients in the feed.

The production of livestock products and the rational use of fodder depend on the quality and quantity of fodder given to cattle, the demand of animals for feed and farm conditions. Cattle are fed according to the established norm. Both underfeeding and overfeeding can have a negative effect on animals. The current feed rate recommended for practical use is based on the general demand of animals for nutrients and is expressed by a feed unit; besides digestible protein, calcium, phosphorus, carotene, table salt norms, about 30 different biologically active substances and supplements are used, depending on the type of animal - enzymes, vitamins, carbohydrates, microelements.

Taking into account the consumption of about 0.5 feed units to produce 1 liter of high-quality milk with a fat content of 4%, the feed rate for dairy cows is calculated. The feed rate is not constant, it is reviewed and changed if necessary, depending on the conditions and the production plan.

Strong feed (concentrated) is an important reserve to increase the share of the nutrient unit in the feed. According to the Research Institute of livestock, poultry and Fisheries of Uzbekistan, compared with the same amount of grain mixture, 100 kg of fully balanced feed fed to livestock allows you to get an additional 25-30kg of milk, 3-4kg of meat, 75-90 eggs.

Figure 1. Income change (mln UZS) in the production of dairy products with high fat content in the farm

Source: statistics of farm in Andijan region

It is explained by the fact that the growth of the gross production of milk and meat in recent years is superior to the growth of total production costs in the same period as factors of economic efficiency increase in the analyzed farm. In fact, as it was mentioned above, the income from the sale of milk has increased by 2.43 times and the income from the sale of meat has increased by 2.5 times due to the production of quality products. The total production costs increased by 2.22 times in 2018-2022. As a result, rentability was ensured at 22.7% due to the production of milk products with high fat content.

It is necessary to pay special attention to the technological factors in the development and effective

organization of the livestock industry in the current and future periods when market competition is intensifying. Increasing the production of quality products in cattle breeding, increasing the productivity of animals depends to a large extent on the supply of mixed feed, which is considered the most important and decisive element of the technology of animal care. That's why, in our opinion, it is advisable to build factories with the capacity to supply livestock with sufficient and standard mixed fodder with the participation of foreign investors.

After all, due to the stable development of livestock breeding in Uzbekistan, increasing the number of livestock with a constant growth trend based on the possibility (power) of creating a quality feed base that can provide a standard level, and increasing their productivity per capita production of quality livestock products such as milk, meat, eggs at the level of medical standards and provision of other sectors of the economy with raw materials of the livestock sector at the expense of domestic resources is of significant socio-economic importance.

It is known that fodder and other types of feed make up the main weight of livestock production costs. Therefore, in the development of animal husbandry, including cattle breeding, the first priority is to strengthen the feed base of the industry, identify and plan its internal and external sources of production, form and diversify infrastructure entities related to feed supply, structural and organizational and taking into account the importance of the role of technical and technological measures, it is necessary to recognize the need for their rational use.

In order to implement the innovative development of livestock industries at the republican level, to form and support the system of training and supply of qualified personnel with higher education suitable for each direction of the sector's activity, to provide material and The step-by-step implementation of measures such as the implementation of mechanisms of moral stimulation is of significant economic and social importance.

A number of innovative mechanisms for the production of high-quality dairy products ensure an increase in efficiency. In particular, it is necessary to increase the weight of dairy cows in the farm herd by 60-70%, to sell bulls under 1 year old for breeding. Also: - it is necessary to achieve a level of fat content of milk above 3.6%. For this, it is necessary to revise the diet of cows, to maintain the microclimate of the farm at the required level; - improvement of agrotechnical breeding and selection of animals with high milk fat content in the herd of cows; - strict adherence to personal hygiene of milkers; - full compliance with all zoohygienic requirements during milking of cows; - wash, disinfect and rinse milking containers and storage containers after each milking; - cooling of freshly milked milk to +4...+5°C; - it is recommended to fully equip milk laboratories and make maximum use of them.

References:

1. Nosirov B.Z. Peculiarities of formation and development of the regional food market (on example of Andijan region. Abstract of the diss. for PhD. T.: SISM, 2004.
2. Юрий Наумов, Игорь Пугач. Проблемы и перспективы развития животноводства в Узбекистане. Discussion paper. 2019. #188. Leibniz Institute of Agricultural Development in Transition Economies (IAMO).
3. Ю.Б.Юсупов, Ц.Лерман, А.С.Чертовицкий, О.М.Акбаров. Ўзбекистонда чорвачилик: бугунги ҳолат, муаммолар ва тараққиёт истикболлари. Аграр секторни ривожлантириш тенденциялари нуқтаи назаридан таҳлил. БМТ Тараққиёт дастури, Ўзбекистон Тошкент 2010.
4. Nosirov B., Mirzakarimov M. Features of development of milk production in Uzbekistan. The scientific heritage. No 91 (2022) p.32-35. ISSN 9215-0365. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6695687.
5. Nosirov B. Some problems of development of livestock industry. Science and education in agriculture. Volume 1, Issue 2. 2022. <https://www.seagc.andqjai.uz>
6. Nosirov B.Z., Ergashev A.A., Islamova D.T. Development prospects of food markets in Andijan province // THEORIA: педагогика, экономика, право. 2020. №1 (1). URL: <https://theoria.apni.ru/article/17-development-prospects-of-food-markets>
7. Sangirova U., Nosirov B., Rahmonova B. Properties and potential of walnut growing in Uzbekistan. JournalNX - A Multidisciplinary Peer Reviewed Journal, Volume 6, Issue 5, Page No. 140-146. ISSN 2581-4230, <https://journalnx.com/papers/20150963-potential-of-walnut.pdf>

8. Nosirov B., Rahmonova B., Islamova D., Yoqubov Sh. The role of increasing the economic efficiency of potato production in food supply of the population of Uzbekistan. Journal of Xi'an University of Architecture & Technology. Volume XIII, Issue 5, 2021. P. 560-567. ISSN: 1006-7930. <https://www.xajzkjdx.cn/gallery/58-may2021.pdf>
9. Nosirov B., Rakhmonova B. Organization of production of walnuts in an industrial volumes. International online conference ECLSS Economics and Social sciences. Proceeding book. June 28-29, 2020. Istanbul, Turkey. P. 59-67. <http://eclss.org/publicationsfordoi/istanbulonline.pdf>
10. B.Nosirov, Sh.Abdullaev, H.Yuldasheva. Relevance of development of multiple-profile farms. International journal for innovative Engineering and Management Research (IJIEMR). 2021. Volume 10, Issue 03, Pages: 516-521. ISSN 2456-5083. <https://ijiemr.org/public/uploads/paper/638741617019191.pdf>
11. B.Nosirov. Features of development of livestock industry in the field of food security. Sustainable agriculture. 3(15).2022. p.17-20. <http://sa.tiiame.uz/en/page/arxiv>
12. B.Nosirov. Basis for the development of the regional food market. ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal. Volume 1(11), 2021. p.65-71.
13. Sangirova U., Nosirov B., Rahmonova B. Organization of walnut production based on the industrial method in Uzbekistan. Sustainable agriculture. 2(6).2020. p.24-26. <http://sa.tiiame.uz/en/page/arxiv>
14. B.Nosirov, A.Raximov. Development of wholesale food markets.American Journal of Science and Learning for Development. Volume 2, No 1. Jan-2023. P. 47-50. ISSN: 2835-2157. <http://inter-publishing.com/index.php/AJSLD/article/view/898>
15. B.Nosirov, A.Abdurashidov. Development of elements of food markets.Web of scientist: International scientific research journal. ISSN: 2776-0979. Volume 4, Issue 3, 2023. P. 881-886. <https://wos.academiascience.org/index.php/wos/article/view/3544/3398>
16. Nosirov B., Nurmatov E. Features of the organization of livestock production in an intensive way.// Web of scientist: International scientific research journal. ISSN: 2776-0979. Volume 4, Issue 8, 2023. P. 84-93. <https://wos.academiascience.org/index.php/wos/article/view/4304>
17. Nosirov B. Chorva naslchiligida iqtisodiy samaradorlikni oshirish yo'llari. //Qishloq xo'jaligida resurs tejoyvchi innovatsion texnologiyalardan samarali foydalanishning ilmiy-amaliy asoslari. AQXAI. 27-28oktabr, 2023. 242-245-b.

Improving quality and efficiency on the basis of production resources in cattle breeding

Bahodirjon Nosirov, Elyorbek Nurmatov

Andijan Institute of Agriculture and Agrotechnologies, Uzbekistan

Email: bahodirjonn@gmail.com

Resume. The production process of livestock products consists of clear, significantly different, and therefore strongly interrelated stages, which requires the creation and coordination of a comprehensive system of factors for the effective development of this industry. This field is interrelated, which embodies the technical, technological, biological, organizational, economic, social, political and legal directions of scientific and technical development, serves to increase the efficiency and quality of production of livestock products at various stages of the production process. And will have a tendency to develop as a result of the influence of important factors and their rational use.

Key words: cattle breeding, livestock, Uzbekistan, quality, efficiency, production resources, factors

It is known that the development of any branch or sector of the society's economy is carried out based on a set of measures developed in various directions, including organizational, structural, administrative, economic, financial, and legal mechanisms and their improvement. In this process, there are many situations, such as the specific characteristics of a particular branch or industry, the principles of organization, the quality and size of the required resources, the degree of interdependence and harmony of the factors that affect the efficiency of their use. consideration has important scientific and practical value. Therefore, in Uzbekistan the goal of the reforms in agriculture is primarily to increase the efficiency of the agro-industrial complex and, in particular, the agricultural sector, as well as the weight of the production of food products and raw materials, on the basis of socio-economic and organizational measures, to increase the export potential of the sector, is expressed in directions such as improving the living conditions of the rural population. Therefore, in the conditions of liberalization and modernization of the economy, researching the scientific-theoretical foundations of sustainable development of the agro-industrial sector, including the livestock sector, and improving the organizational-economic mechanisms are of priority.

Organizational factors that include improving the breeding of animals in livestock farms, forming and increasing groups of animals of each breed, strengthening the supply of fodder and developing the system of zoo-veterinary services; economic and legal factors consisting of existing mutual production - contractual - financial relations in the system of production, preparation, processing and sale of livestock products; environmental factors caused by deterioration of the composition and quality of food crops as a result of increased salinity of land and water resources; inadequate application of technical-technological activities, including intensive development of the industry at the expense of mechanization of production and reduction of manual labor; urgent issues such as the incomplete use of social factors, including the consumption system, and the sharp deterioration of the supply of livestock with natural fodder are emerging.

The organizational and economic mechanism of livestock development consists mainly of organizational, economic, technological and legal structure elements that are used directly and indirectly in the process of managing the network, and it needs to solve two interrelated problems. Firstly, it is required to produce and sell livestock products in the required volume, and secondly, to create conditions for efficient operation of economic entities and high income.

In the process of improving the organizational and economic mechanism of effective development of cattle breeding on the basis of quality products, priority should be given to eliminating the following problems in the future:

- development of the infrastructure of the cattle breeding network, effective management of the market of food, raw materials and agricultural products in a harmonious manner within the framework of mutually beneficial relations;
- organization of breeding work at the level of modern requirements;

- placement and specialization of the network based on the natural climate and soil conditions of the regions;
- creating conditions for agricultural producers to freely enter foreign food markets with their consumer goods and to export them and provide appropriate benefits;
- effective use of the elements of the economic mechanism that creates the possibility of expanded reproduction in the network and achieving the level of profitability;
- development and implementation of investment projects for modernization and diversification of activities of livestock production entities based on innovative techniques and technologies;
- Provision of information resources on best practices of foreign countries related to animal husbandry, including cattle breeding development, improvement of product quality and cost reduction, organization of foreign trips for qualification improvement.

In order to develop the livestock industry, improve the quality of meat and dairy products, reduce costs, and increase the efficiency of the industry, first of all, special attention should be paid to the measures to fully provide it with all relevant factors and resources. At the same time, it is appropriate to recognize that there are a number of tasks that cannot be postponed and are waiting for their solution now and in the near future. Among them, first of all, it is necessary to place the network and diversify its activities in accordance with the regional natural and climatic conditions, to build large dairy and dairy complexes, to expand the possibility of their innovative development, including modern, including foreign advanced scientific and technical achievements, introduction of waste-free nanotechnologies, expansion of the range of finished livestock consumer products on the basis of increasing processing capacity, finding sources and channels for their export, development of roadmaps for step-by-step solutions to problems such as their effective use can be included.

The production process of livestock products consists of clear, significantly different, and therefore strongly interrelated stages, which requires the creation and coordination of a comprehensive system of factors for the effective development of this industry. This field is interrelated, which embodies the technical, technological, biological, organizational, economic, social, political and legal directions of scientific and technical development, serves to increase the efficiency and quality of production of livestock products at various stages of the production process. And will have a tendency to develop as a result of the influence of important factors and their rational use.

In general, in the case of farms, it is necessary to focus on solving the following important tasks related to the development of the livestock sector at the national level: the main basis for the sustainable development of livestock networks, including the cattle industry, is the creation of a feed base and its direct dependence on the structural enrichment of rations. Therefore, first of all, to increase the level of their satiety and digestion by placing feed crops in agricultural farms within the framework of a scientifically based crop rotation system in order to form internal feed resources, increasing their productivity, feeding cattle on scientific-based rations, improving the quality of feed and enriching them with nutrients, building industrialized new enterprises producing, it is necessary to pay attention to such as providing qualified technical personnel.

Figure 1. Factors that ensure economic efficiency by improving the quality of products on the farm

In the near future (2-3 years) in Uzbekistan and its regions, deepening and accelerating structural-organizational reforms covering the strategy of innovative development of the livestock sector, including the cattle industry, its stages, conceptual foundations and directions, financing of this process it is necessary to develop road maps aimed at identifying sources and institutions, including finding and attracting foreign investors who invest directly in this sector, introducing a system of additional benefits for them and improving the methods and mechanisms.

In order to effectively develop the livestock sector based on quality products, the main focus is on measures for the rational use of all important factors that embody and interconnect natural-climatic, bio-ecological, technical-technological, organizational-economic, socio-legal directions focus is necessary.

Due to the increase in the number of heads of large-horned cattle, the proportion of breeding, high-yielding cattle brought from foreign countries increases from year to year, and this event is laying the groundwork for the development of the cattle industry due to an intensive factor, i.e. increased productivity, a stable increase in the production of quality meat and dairy products.

On the basis of private entrepreneurship in regions with large rural centers and developed livestock, attention should be paid to conducting auctions specializing in the sale of mixed feed, coarse cartilage and other types of feed, pedigree goods, to the organization and development of branches specializing in zooveterinary and breeding work, aviary and other types of services.

Due to the relatively low income of livestock farms in our country, it is advisable to organize the application of mechanisms to stimulate the state financing of researches in the areas of breeding, fodder farming, production of necessary techniques and technologies for the livestock network, as well as the rapid implementation into production.

Because of the potential of natural and economic resources for the development of livestock sectors in the Republic and the production of quality environmentally friendly livestock products, it is necessary to look at the export of livestock products as one of the most influential mechanisms in the future for state support and promotion.

Due to the potential of natural and economic resources for the development of livestock industries and the production of high-quality ecologically clean livestock products in Uzbekistan, it is necessary to consider state support and encouragement of the export of livestock products as one of the effective mechanisms in the

future.

References:

1. Nosirov B.Z. Peculiarities of formation and development of the regional food market (on example of Andijan region. Abstract of the diss. for PhD. T.: SISM, 2004.
2. Юрий Наумов, Игорь Пугач. Проблемы и перспективы развития животноводства в Узбекистане. Discussion paper. 2019. #188. Leibniz Institute of Agricultural Development in Transition Economies (IAMO).
3. Ю.Б.Юсупов. Ц.Лерман, А.С.Чертовицкий, О.М.Акбаров. Ўзбекистонда чорвачилик: бугунги ҳолат, муаммолар ва тараққиёт истикболлари. Аграр секторни ривожлантириш тенденциялари нуқтаи назаридан таҳлил. БМТ Тараққиёт дастури, Ўзбекистон Тошкент 2010.
4. Nosirov B., Mirzakarimov M. Features of development of milk production in Uzbekistan. The scientific heritage. No 91 (2022) p.32-35. ISSN 9215-0365. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6695687.
5. Nosirov B. Some problems of development of livestock industry. Science and education in agriculture. Volume 1, Issue 2. 2022. <https://www.seagc.andqjai.uz>
6. Nosirov B.Z., Ergashev A.A., Islamova D.T. Development prospects of food markets in Andijan province // THEORIA: педагогика, экономика, право. 2020. №1 (1). URL: <https://theoria.apni.ru/article/17-development-prospects-of-food-markets>
7. Sangirova U., Nosirov B., Rahmonova B. Properties and potential of walnut growing in Uzbekistan. JournalNX - A Multidisciplinary Peer Reviewed Journal, Volume 6, Issue 5, Page No. 140-146. ISSN 2581-4230, <https://journalnx.com/papers/20150963-potential-of-walnut.pdf>
8. Nosirov B., Rahmonova B., Islamova D., Yoqubov Sh. The role of increasing the economic efficiency of potato production in food supply of the population of Uzbekistan. Journal of Xi'an University of Architecture & Technology. Volume XIII, Issue 5, 2021. P. 560-567. ISSN: 1006-7930. <https://www.xajzkjdx.cn/gallery/58-may2021.pdf>
9. Nosirov B., Rakhmonova B. Organization of production of walnuts in an industrial volumes. International online conference ECLSS Economics and Social sciences. Proceeding book. June 28-29, 2020. Istanbul, Turkey. P. 59-67. <http://eclss.org/publicationsfordoi/istanbulonline.pdf>
10. B.Nosirov, Sh.Abdullaev, H.Yuldasheva. Relevance of development of multiple-profile farms. International journal for innovative Engineering and Management Research (IJIEMR). 2021. Volume 10, Issue 03, Pages: 516-521. ISSN 2456-5083. <https://ijiemr.org/public/uploads/paper/638741617019191.pdf>
11. B.Nosirov. Features of development of livestock industry in the field of food security. Sustainable agriculture. 3(15).2022. p.17-20. <http://sa.tiame.uz/en/page/arxiv>
12. B.Nosirov. Basis for the development of the regional food market. ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal. Volume 1(11), 2021. p.65-71.
13. Sangirova U., Nosirov B., Rahmonova B. Organization of walnut production based on the industrial method in Uzbekistan. Sustainable agriculture. 2(6).2020. p.24-26. <http://sa.tiame.uz/en/page/arxiv>
14. B.Nosirov, A.Raximov. Development of wholesale food markets.American Journal of Science and Learning for Development. Volume 2, No 1. Jan-2023. P. 47-50. ISSN: 2835-2157. <http://inter-publishing.com/index.php/AJSLD/article/view/898>
15. B.Nosirov, A.Abdurashidov. Development of elements of food markets.Web of scientist: International scientific research journal. ISSN: 2776-0979. Volume 4, Issue 3, 2023. P. 881-886. <https://wos.academiascience.org/index.php/wos/article/view/3544/3398>
16. Nosirov B., Nurmatov E. Features of the organization of livestock production in an intensive way.// Web of scientist: International scientific research journal. ISSN: 2776-0979. Volume 4, Issue 8, 2023. P. 84-93. <https://wos.academiascience.org/index.php/wos/article/view/4304>
17. Nosirov B. Chorva naslchiligida iqtisodiy samaradorlikni oshirish yo'llari. //Qishloq xo'jaligida resurs tejovchi innovatsion texnologiyalardan samarali foydalanishninig ilmiy-amaliy asoslari. AQXAI. 27-28oktabr, 2023. 242-245-b.

Services Of A. Orinboev In Cataloging Works

Burkhanov Ilyaskhan Mukhiddinovich,
PhD student of Fergana State University
Burkhanov Ilyaskhan Mukhiddinovich,
Graduate student of Fergana State University

Abstract: The article highlights the issue of cataloging and publishing the works of A. Urinboev in his scientific activities, analyzes the scientist's contribution to the cataloging of manuscripts stored at the Institute of Oriental Studies of the UzSC.

Key words: Catalog, manuscript, east, publication, order, institution.

The issue of cataloging and classification of oriental manuscripts is of great importance in the scientific heritage of Asomiddin Orinboev. He actively participated in the creation and publication of seven catalogs of the source fund of the Institute of Oriental Manuscripts under the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan. In addition, he managed to create and publish a catalog based on five foreign projects at the international level. In the analysis of the scientist's achievements in this field, the history of the catalog and its creation was briefly discussed.

The word catalog is defined as follows: "Catalog - (Greek katalogos list) means a list of certain items, such as books, exhibits, products, given in a certain order. For example, stamps, works of art, a library catalog, a place where file names are stored in the logical device of computer programs, a collection of files. can be said to have created the catalog.

The oldest catalog that has survived to this day is a collection of documents collected by Ashurbanipal of Assyria in the 7th century BC. Language, summary of the text, title, author's name, code of the library where the document is stored, i.e. number are written on each of its plates [1-5]. One of the interesting facts about the wall catalog: it was recorded on the wall of the building about the funds of the library of the Temple of Horus, founded in 239 BC. The study of these data in a certain sense helps in the research of the scientific heritage of Asomiddin Orinboev. The catalogs compiled and edited by the scientist were able to combine ancient experience and new science. Catalogs are in the form of a thick book, with several descriptions written for each source, the date the source was written and copied by the calligrapher, whether there is another copy of it, the quality of the paper on which the manuscript was copied and the quality of the paper on which the manuscript was copied, and in some cases even the place of production of the paper, the number it is kept. given in detail. In scientific news, on the initiative of Asomiddin Orinboev, the sources of the Institute of Oriental Studies of the UzR FA have been thematized and turned into a catalog [6-10].

G. Karimov had great difficulty in finding a unique source and "Cataloging of manuscripts, i.e. compiling a brief description of works in manuscript books and publishing them in the form of books, has been one of the most important scientific tasks of this institution since 1943, when the Institute of Oriental Studies named after Abu Rayhan Beruni of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan was established [11-15].", he noted. In doing so, he pointed to the ease with which every researcher can easily find and use the desired source with the help of the catalog. Because he said that he could not find the necessary source even in foreign countries, and that it was difficult to find it in Uzbekistan using the catalog. Asomiddin Orinboev is commendable for facilitating the work of such researchers and scientists and organizing existing manuscripts. But although such work is actually a complex process, for a person looking from the outside, these efforts are not noticeable. Let's imagine that if there is no catalog, one can spend several months to find a single source among more than eleven thousand manuscripts. Based on the directory, you will have that resource in five minutes. Only a person who has gone through this process can deeply understand how convenient and light it is, and appreciate the work of the scientists who compiled the catalog and prepared it for publication.

Academician D. Yusupova was also interviewed several times regarding the issue of cataloging of manuscripts by Asomiddin Orinboev. "Before Uzbekistan gained independence, an 11-volume catalog was published based on the sources available in the manuscript fund of our Institute of Oriental Studies. Theirs

Volumes V and VI were prepared by Aka Asomiddin himself with descriptions. [16-20] Currently, these catalogs are almost not used in scientific circulation. Because, after independence, they were published in a new and convenient way. Nevertheless, based on the research objective, the eleven-volume catalog was thoroughly studied.

According to Professor A. Semenov, when writing the descriptions of the manuscripts included in volume V prepared for publication in 1960, S.A. Azimjonova, V.I. Belyaev, E. Betger, D. Voronovsky, V. Zhukov, A. Qayumov, A. Kononov, N Mikluho-Maklay, A. Molchanov, K. Munirov, T. Nigmatov, Z. Rizaev, M. Sale, A. Semenov, O. Smirnova, K. Starkova, S. Tveritina, A. Orinboev, A. Shmitlar actively participated [21-25].

The fifth volume of the catalog includes sections entitled history, biography (biographical score), act and epigraphy, memoirs and fiction, each of which contains a classification of manuscripts related to the field.

According to the scientist D. Voronovsky, who wrote the introduction to volume VI of Eastern manuscripts published in 1963, the descriptions of fifty-two manuscripts included in this collection were written by Asomiddin Orinboev [26-30]. Thirty-two of them were included in the catalog with repetition, and as a result, 84 descriptions belonged to Asomiddin Orinboev.

In 1964, the VII volume of the aforementioned catalog was published under the editorship of candidate of historical sciences Asomiddin Orinboev and candidate of philological sciences L.M. Epifanov. The description of the manuscripts included in this collection was prepared by A. Qayumov, K. Munirov, T. Nigmatova, A. Orinboev. A total of 608 manuscripts are described in it, most of them belong to the literary literature of the XIV-XX centuries. Manuscripts in the poetry department are works of the 14th-20th centuries, and among their authors there are literary representatives such as Navoi, Lutfiy, Sakkokiy, Durbek [31-35].

List of used literature

1. National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan. Volume IV. - Tashkent: State Scientific Publishing House, 2002. - B. 500. (Total 703.)
2. Florov Yu. Iz istorii biblioteknykh katalogov // Nauka i jizn. No. 6. – Russia, 2022. For more information, see: <https://www.nkj.ru/archive/articles/44638/>
3. Yusupova D. Asomiddin Urinbaev. - Tashkent, 2004. - S. 11.
4. Karimov G'. The Prophet's Bag: An Essay // Eastern Star. – 2010. – No. 4. – B. 131-137.
5. Oral history from Academician Yusupova D.Yu.
6. *Sobranie vostochnykh rukopisey AN UzSSR (series, annotated directory)*. - T. I. - Tashkent: Izd-vo AN UzSSR, 1952. - S. 440; - T. II. - S. 590; - T. III. - S. 553; - T. IV. - S.560; - T. V. – S.543. - T. VI. - S. 737; - T. VII. - S. 554; - T. VIII. - S. 798; - T. IX. - S.600; - T. X. – S.705; - T. XI. - S.444.
7. *Sobranie vostochnykh rukopisey AN UzSSR (serial, annotated catalog)*. T. V. - Tashkent: Izd-vo AN UzSSR, 1963. - S. 8.
8. D. Voronovsky. Predislovie. *Sobranie vostochnykh rukopisey AN UzSSR (serial, annotated catalog)*. T. VI. - Tashkent: Izd-vo AN UzSSR, 1963. - S. 10.
9. Vahabova B. Written by Ibn Siny and sobranii AN RUz (catalogue). / Otv. ed. A. Urunbaev. - Tashkent: Science, 1982. - 71 p.
10. Хатамова, З. (2021). Expenditure of income from taxes and levies in the kokand khanate: <https://doi.org/10.47100/conferences.v1i1.1230>. In *research support center conferences* (No. 18.05).
11. Nazirjonovna, K. Z. (2022). SH. VOKHIDOV'S CONTRIBUTION TO THE STUDY OF THE HISTORY OF THE KOKAND KHANATE. *Innovative Society: Problems, Analysis and Development Prospects*, 139-141.
12. Xatamova, Z. (2021, June). EXPENDITURE OF INCOME FROM TAXES AND LEVIES IN THE KOKAND KHANATE. In *Конференции*.
13. Хатамова, З. (2023). Из истории денежной политики в финансовой системе Кокандского ханства. *Актуальные проблемы истории Узбекистана*, 1(1), 327–336. извлечено от <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/history-of-uzbekistan/article/view/16511>
14. Nazirjonovna, K. Z. (2022). Political-Financial Analysis of the Issues of Science of the Kokand Khanate in the Work of Khudoyorkhonzade “Anjum At-Tavorikh”. *CENTRAL ASIAN JOURNAL OF*

- SOCIAL SCIENCES AND HISTORY*, 3(10), 102-111. Retrieved from <https://cajssh.centralasianstudies.org/index.php/CAJSSH/article/view/463>
15. Burkhonov, I. M. (2020). "ZAKAT" HAS ENSURED FAIRNESS AND BALANCE IN SOCIETY. *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (5), 201-204.
 16. Muhiddinovich, B. I. (2020). Negative impact of the tax system on political life-on the example of the history of the Kokand Khanate (1850–1865). *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 10(5), 790-795.
 17. Burkhonov, I. (2021, June). The importance of the scientific heritage of asomiddin urinboev in the study of the history of the Kokand khanat. In *Конференции*.
 18. Burkhonov, I. (2021). The importance of the scientific heritage of asomiddin urinboev in the study of the history of the Kokand khanat: <https://doi.org/10.47100/conferences.v1i1.1242>. In *RESEARCH SUPPORT CENTER CONFERENCES* (No. 18.05).
 19. Бурханов, И. (2023). Научное наследие Шарафиддина Али Язди в интерпретации Асомиддина Оринбоева. *Актуальные проблемы истории Узбекистана*, 1(1), 165–171.
 20. BURKHONOV, I. FROM THE HISTORY OF THE TRANSLATION OF THE WORK OF ABURAZZAK SAMARKAND" MATLA'I SA'DAYN AND MAJMA'I BAHRAIN. *ЭКОНОМИКА*, 138-144.
 21. Muhiddinovich, B. I. (2022). The Importance of Asomiddin Urinboev's Scientific Research in the Study of the History of the Kokan Khanate. *Kresna Social Science and Humanities Research*, 3, 175-179.
 22. Muhiddinovich, B. I. (2022). In the Study of the History of the Kokand Khanate. *Eurasian Journal of History, Geography and Economics*, 6, 68-71.
 23. Burkhanov, I. (2022). FROM THE HISTORY OF THE USE OF THE SCIENTIFIC HERITAGE OF KOKAND SCIENTISTS ASOMIDDIN URINBOEV. *International Bulletin of Medical Sciences and Clinical Research*, 2(10), 63–67.
 24. Хатамова, З. (2021, August). EXPENDITURE OF INCOME FROM TAXES AND LEVIES IN THE KOKAND KHANATE: <https://doi.org/10.47100/conferences.v1i1.1230>. In *RESEARCH SUPPORT CENTER CONFERENCES* (No. 18.05).
 25. Хатамова, З. Н. Особенности налоговой системы Кокандского ханства / З. Н. Хатамова. — Текст : непосредственный // Молодой ученый. — 2020. — № 5 (295). — С. 254-256. — URL: <https://moluch.ru/archive/295/66918/>
 26. Nazirjonovna, H. Z., & Abdumannobovich, N. M. (2020). Tax system on the territory of kyrgyzstan during the Kokand Khanate. *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 10(6), 209-212.
 27. Xatamova, Z. (2020). Expenditure of state funds replenished by taxes in the history of the kokand khanate. *EPRA International Journal of Research and Development (IJRD)*, 5(3), 274-277.
 28. Nazirjonovna, K. Z. ., & Odinakhan, A. . (2023). PEDAGOGICAL SKILLS AND THEIR TYPES. *JOURNAL OF SCIENCE, RESEARCH AND TEACHING*, 2(5), 18–21.
 29. Khatamova, Z. N., & Almamatova, N. (2023). SPECIFIC CHARACTERISTICS OF PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES. *Innovative Development in Educational Activities*, 2(9), 19–23
 30. Nazirjonovna, K. Z. ., & Abduvaxitovich, A. A. . (2023). APPLICATION OF MODERN TECHNOLOGIES AND ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN EDUCATION AND ITS FUTURE . *IJTIMOIIY FANLARDA INNOVASIYA ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI*, 3(5), 98–104.
 31. Sh. Kholmatov. (2023). THE FORMATION OF SPIRITUALITY AND ITS IMPORTANCE IN THE CONSTRUCTION OF CIVIL SOCIETY. *European Journal of Interdisciplinary Research and Development*, 16, 430–436.
 32. Khatamova Zumradkhon Nazirjanovna. (2022, май 19). COVERING THE EMBASSY ISSUES OF THE KOKAND KHANATE IN HISTORICAL SOURCE "ANJUM AT-TAVORIX". INNOVATION IN THE MODERN EDUCATION SYSTEM, Washington, USA. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6564783>

-
33. .Kholmatov, S. (2023). *STUDYING THE PROBLEM OF SOCIAL ADAPTATION OF STUDENTS IN HIGHER EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS. В INTERNATIONAL BULLETIN OF APPLIED SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY (Т. 3, Выпуск 10, сс. 468–471).*
 34. Sh. Kholmatov. (2023). *THE FORMATION OF SPIRITUALITY AND ITS IMPORTANCE IN THE CONSTRUCTION OF CIVIL SOCIETY. European Journal of Interdisciplinary Research and Development, 16, 430–436.*
 35. .Хатамова , З. (2023). ЛИТЕРАТУРНЫЕ КУРСЫ ДЛЯ ИНЖЕНЕРОВ: ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ ТВОРЧЕСКОГО МЫШЛЕНИЯ И КОММУНИКАТИВНЫХ НАВЫКОВ. *Conference on Digital Innovation : "Modern Problems and Solutions".* извлечено от <https://fer-teach.uz/index.php/codimpas/article/view/1763>
 36. .Хатамова, З., & Umaraliyeva , М. (2023). О‘QUVCHILARNI МА’NAVIY-AXLOQIY TARBIYALASH. *Ilm-Fan Va ta’lim, 1(7).* извлечено от <https://ilmfanvatalim.uz/index.php/ift/article/view/196>
 37. Nazirjonovna, H. Z., & Sobirjonovna, Q. D. (2020). Important sources in studying the tax system of the Kokand Khanate. *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal, 10(5), 803-808.*

The Essence Of Michelle Montin's Philosophical Views

Kurbonov Umidjon Egamberdiyevich

Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Philosophical Sciences, Associate Professor

Uzbek-Finnish Pedagogical Institute (Uzbekistan)

E-mail: umidjon.kurbonov.81@gmail.com

Abstract: The article examines the socio-philosophical views of Michel Montaigne, the greatest thinker of the European Renaissance, the great philosopher and humanist in the cultural development of 16th century France, his contribution to the development of the literary-philosophical and linguistic-cultural thought of his time.

Key words: Renaissance, humanist, Enlightenment movement Michel Montaigne, "Experiments", philosophy, ethics.

Introduction

Michel Montaigne, the greatest thinker of the European Renaissance, a famous public and political figure, had a great influence on the development of literary-philosophical and linguocultural thought of his time and is rightly considered the last humanist of the Renaissance and the first moralist of the new era. He was an encyclopaedist, an educated man who continued to develop the traditions of antiquity, taking into account a number of theoretical and cognitive problems, while emphasising that the cognitive process should serve both the achievement of reliable knowledge and the formation of human morality.

Particular attention should be paid to the development of cultural and philosophical ideas during the Renaissance, a special place in the development of scientific and philosophical thought is occupied by the 16th century as the second stage of the new era. During this period, the centre of science shifted to France as the Enlightenment movement spread widely in the late 16th and early 17th centuries. The French Enlightenment is characterised by the following:

1. Has an international character;
2. He was on the side against feudalism;
3. Anti-religious, anti-clerical;
4. A firm believer in the power of science;
5. Looking to the future with optimism;

Materials and Methods

The French Enlightenment was much more developed than the Enlightenment in other countries (America, Germany, Russia, etc.).

The great philosopher and humanist Michel Montaigne had his own place and views in the cultural development of 16th century France.

At first glance, Montaigne's philosophy seems somewhat strange, unusual, and different from the ordinary; the thinker's thoughts on laws, morality, and religion are all interspersed with descriptions of the events of everyday life. Montaigne takes the reader into the innermost recesses of his heart, confides to him his pains and habits; he does not conceal faults, even those that might seem reprehensible. All this is done with appealing seriousness and a sense of responsibility. He doesn't care what people look like, he wants to be honest, encouraging others to preserve themselves and not outdo others, and he is the first to follow this rule.

Results

Montaigne himself considers the work "Experiments" mainly a philosophical work. He opposes the "accepted" philosophy, in the sense of philosophy relegated to the level of empty words, irrelevant to life, alien to the real problems of human morality, describing it as follows: "It is strange that philosophy in our time, even for thinking people, is only an empty word, meaning nothing; such philosophy finds no use and has no value in anyone's eyes or in practice. [1; P.204].

In Book I, Chapter XIX of the Experiments, Montaigne ponders the idea that "man cannot judge whether he is happy until death" and in Chapter XX, "To think philosophically is to learn how to die" [2; P.704]. He is characterized by adherence to ancient worldview traditions: it is forbidden to assess the happiness of a person until death. Here the thinker turns to the stories of King Croesus, Agesilaus and others, referring to cases of brave and famous deaths. Montaigne takes a very philosophical approach to the question of death, when assessing the lives of others, he concludes that he always considers what his end is, and as such his greatest hope is that his life will end well enough, that is, quietly and unnoticed. From this point of view, Montaigne's thoughts on the subject of preparation for death harmonize with those of Plato and Cicero. As the author notes, the meaning and purpose of philosophy, in most cases, this science teaches people not to be afraid of approaching death. [3; P.76].

Montaigne, in the spirit of the ancient Stoics, generalizes the fact of waiting for death and connects it with freedom. If man is able to learn to die (not to fear death), then he has the ability to live freely.

Although the author does not say so explicitly in his work, it is clear that there is an inner text, that is, in the text - what is called philosophy in the universities is an alien mask, a phenomenon that causes fear. To Montaigne, a man of the new humanist culture, scholastic philosophy seems empty, meaningless, insubstantial. A philosophy that is universally accepted and not subjected to an independent examination of ideas cannot claim to be true. The thinker believes that the original origins of rational philosophy are in classical antiquity. According to Montaigne, ancient philosophy is true because of the distinction between "thought and freedom", as a consequence of which "several schools were formed both in philosophy and in the humanities, and each man followed his own judgement and chose among them what he needed". [4; P. 297].

Conclusion

In conclusion, Montaigne as a thinker was formed at the decline of the cultural movement called Renaissance humanism that was widespread in Europe. Montaigne was one of the first to get rid of medieval superstitions and their rotten clothes. The thinker has a sense of enjoyment of life, a heightened sensitivity to the pleasures and enjoyment that life is full of, and the wisdom of the ancient world brought him a ratio of proportions, a need for harmony, and an outlook of perception of the world.

Montaigne suggests that man cannot hide from his "I" because he always acts within the framework of his accompanying vices and faults. From this point of view, the process of solitude, which represents the empty spatiality of the "I", cannot save the soul from evil, from the "characteristics of the crowd" ingrained in it, cannot save it from external inferiority, and deprives man of the pleasure of his immediate life activity. [5; P.176].

In conclusion, it can be said that Montaigne conducted research throughout his life on such issues as law, education, friendship, kindness to parents, freedom of conscience, and self-control. The importance of the thinker's legacy is that it is highly valued not only in France, but also as a unique intellectual property throughout the world.

References:

1. Michel Montaigne. Experiments. T.I-III. – M., 1958-1960. P.204.
2. Michel Montaigne. Experiments. – Book. 1, 2. – M.: Science, 1979. P.702.
3. Michel Montaigne. Experiments. – Book. 1, 2. – M.: Science, 1979. P.76.
4. Michel Montaigne. Experiments. T.I-III. – M., 1958-1960. P.297.
5. Maliyeva T.I. «Experiments» of M. Montaigne on the art of living well / T.I. Maliyeva, Z.H. Totrova // Contemporary research on social problems.– 2016. – № 3–3(27). – P. 176.
6. Umidjon K. " EGO" OF MONTAIGNE THROUGH PERSONALLY CONSTITUTED INTERNAL EXPERIENCE //Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal. – 2021. – T. 9. – №. 9. – C. 105-110.
7. Kurbanov U. MICHEL DE MONTAIGNE ON THE EXPERIENCE OF SELF-KNOWLEDGE //Conferencious Online. – 2021. – C. 39-41.
8. Alikulov X., Haqulov N. Q. Spiritual maturity and philosophical thinking dependence of development //ISJ Theoretical & Applied Science. – 2020. – T. 4. – №. 84. – C. 164-167.

9. Хаққулов Н. Қ. Perfect generation-personality of private education and humanity facilities //Мировая наука. – 2019. – №. 2 (23). – С. 62-63.
10. Ризаев И. И., Хаккулов Н. К. ВЛИЯНИЕ ЦИФРОВОЙ КУЛЬТУРЫ НА НЕПРИКОСНОВЕННОСТЬ ЖИЗНИ ЧЕЛОВЕКА В ОБЩЕСТВЕ //Оргкомитет. – 2023. – С. 342.
11. Abduraxmonovich A. A. Thinkers of the Muslim East on Commercial Ethics //Czech Journal of Multidisciplinary Innovations. – 2022. – Т. 12. – С. 56-60.
12. Umidzhon K. European renaissance and Michelle Montaigne: the way of man's understanding himself //Вісник Маріупольського державного університету. Сер.: Філософія, культурологія, соціологія. – 2019. – №. 18. – С. 50-57.
13. Курбонов У. ПУТЬ ПОСТИЖЕНИЯ ЧЕЛОВЕКОМ САМОГО СЕБЯ КАК КЛЮЧЕВОЙ ПАФОС «ОПЫТОВ» М. МОНТЕНЯ //ІЛМІҮ АХВОРОТНОМА. – С. 62.
14. Bekbutaevna B. M. IMPROVEMENT OF INNOVATIVE MECHANISMS OF THE ORGANIZATION OF SOCIAL EDUCATION IN FAMILIES //Spectrum Journal of Innovation, Reforms and Development. – 2022. – Т. 7. – С. 36-39.
15. Amridinova D. T. THE IDEA OF A PERFECT PERSON IN OUR SPIRITUAL HERITAGE (ON THE EXAMPLE OF THE DOCTRINE OF ACCELERATION) //Scientific and Technical Journal of Namangan Institute of Engineering and Technology. – 2020. – Т. 2. – №. 7. – С. 171-176.
16. UTKIROVNA J. N. Pedagogical Innovation and Integration in the Educational Process of Primary Education //JournalNX. – Т. 6. – №. 09. – С. 250-253.
17. JAMALOVA N. Pedagogical Conditions for the Development of Individual-Personal Characteristics of Students of a Higher Educational Institution //PINDUS Journal of Culture, Literature, and ELT (PJCLE). – 2022.
18. Utkirovna J. N. POSSIBILITIES OF USE OF FOLK PEDAGOGY IN THE FORMATION OF INDIVIDUAL AND PERSONAL CHARACTERISTICS OF STUDENTS //Spectrum Journal of Innovation, Reforms and Development. – 2022. – Т. 10. – С. 66-69.
19. Yuldasheva S. The Main Directions of the Organization of Production Processes at Industrial Enterprises in the Digital Economy //Central Asian Journal of Theoretical and Applied Science. – 2021. – Т. 2. – №. 4. – С. 189-194.
20. Karimova N. M. et al. Pedagogical Conditions for Students to use Critical Thinking in the Development of Interethnic Communication //Journal of Survey in Fisheries Sciences. – 2023. – Т. 10. – №. 2S. – С. 4211-4219.

The Attractiveness Of Muhammad Yusuf's Poetry

Ma'rifatov Khursandbek

Is an 11th-grade student of general secondary education school No. 38, which has in-depth classes in some subjects, belonging to the Preschool and School Education Department of Amudarya District of the Republic of Karakalpakstan.

Annotation; Muhammad Yusuf, who was born in a simple peasant family, entered the world of creativity and the spiritual and spiritual significance of his creative works in human life.

Key Words; Muhammad Yusuf, artistic analysis of his poetry, his achievements, the place of his works in world literature.

Introduction; Uzbek literature is rich in such elegant poets and poetesses that it is like a big field. In this Boston, a generation of charming poets, who are not similar to each other and do not repeat each other, grows up again and again. One of such unique poets was, undoubtedly, Muhammad Yusuf, the national poet of Uzbekistan, the nightingale child of our nation. He was born on April 26, 1954 in the village of Qovunchi in the Marhamat district of the Andijan region in a family of ordinary hardworking people. He spent his innocent childhood and joyful adolescence in this village. After receiving high school education, Muhammad Yusuf entered the Institute of Russian Language and Literature in Tashkent and graduated in 1978. Samples of his first poems were published in 1976 in the pages of the "Literature and Art of Uzbekistan" weekly. At that time, Uzbek poetry reached a new level of growth, and a unique creative competition between many talents such as Shavkat Rahman, Usman Azim, Khurshid Davron was in full swing. It was not an easy task to boldly enter this circle of creativity and take a suitable place. Muhammad Yusuf was one of the poets who succeeded in this task and was able to attract the attention of the public forever.

In 1978-1980, the young artist worked in the "Book Lovers" society of the republic, in 1980-1986 in the "Tashkent Evening" newspaper of the capital, and in 1986-1992 in the Literary and Art Publishing House named after Gafur Ghulam. The years of working in this publishing house played an important role in the creative destiny of Muhammad Yusuf. Because at that time, Erkin Vahidov, one of the greatest creators of his time, was in charge of this dargah, and the spirit of creativity that prevailed in all departments gave a serious impetus to the development of the young poet. Muhammad Yusuf tried hard to prove himself as a poet among his pen friends and teachers who created memorable works in various directions of poetry. In 1992-1995, Muhammad Yusuf worked in the "Voice of Uzbekistan" newspaper and the National Information Agency of Uzbekistan (Uz A). Since 1997, the poet has been appointed deputy chairman of the Writers' Union of Uzbekistan. Although his poems were often published in periodicals, his first poetry collection was published relatively late in 1985. After that, the poet wrote "I have something to say to Nightingale" (1987), "Iltijo" (1988), "Girl at Home" (1989), "Halima enam allalari" (1989), "Ishq kemasi" (1990), "One from my heart". yor" (1990), "Bewafo kop ekkan" (1991), "Yolgonchi yor", "Erka kiyik" (1992), "I will take you to my sky" and dozens of poetry collections are in the hands of the reader. arrived. He created epics such as "The End of the Sky" and "The Black Sun" by referring to major poetic genres.

The independence of our country opened new horizons in Muhammad Yusuf's work. His beautiful poems in honor of the nation and the country's independence echoed in the hearts of millions with their sincerity, simplicity, and artistic excellence. Dozens of the poet's poems such as "My country", "Khalq bol, elim", "Dunyo", "Insha'Allah", "Uzbekmomo", "Ikror" are works that prove how true poetry should sing the country. became As for the poet's first poetry collection, the first poetry collection called "Familiar Poplars" was published in 1985. No matter which of the poet's poems are analyzed, he always exudes uniqueness, attractiveness, and also love for the motherland and motherland. If we consider the poet's artistic analysis of the poem "Yurtim, unfulfilled dreams"...

MY GUY, YOU HAVE INCREDIBLE DREAMS...

My country, you have unfulfilled dreams,
You have stories that made the stones cry,

My soul hurts thinking about your past,
Your chest is full of martyred sons.

My heart gives me a thought of spring days,
The moon shines in the evenings.
Akmal Ikramlar, who was innocent
You have brave fields like Faizullah...

My country, you have skies as wide as your heart,
You have stories that made the star cry.
It is harder for you to see than your heavens,
You have shepherds who look like gazelles.

Press my face on the palm of your hand,
Mother, don't take my word hard,
Birch leaves covered his eyes
You have the Ottomans who are far away.

Alhazar, alhazar, a thousand times alhazar,
Look, what they're wearing when they walk
Those who bought the qadiri and became poets-
You have scorpions coming out of your mouth...

Be your sacrifice, my mother,
Your cries are my cry,
My soul hurts thinking about your past,
I can tell you that you have great stories.

You have learned from history that the Uzbek nation is one of the oldest nations in the world. And this nation experienced unprecedented events in history. It is located between two rivers, the land is fertile, the people are hardworking, and there is no one who has not been fascinated by this land, which has created unique examples of friendly culture. Invaders came after the invaders and tried to plunder this beautiful country - to steal its wealth and enslave its people. Our nation has survived all the tests like the samandar (a mythical bird that is born in the fire and survives the fire) and came out with honor. However, these struggles, aspirations for freedom, of course, did not pass without victims and losses. The national values, the original children of the nation, who knew the freedom of the country above all else, died on these battlefields. As rice is not without puddles, unfortunately, history does not forget those who turned themselves aside when the time came, lost their honor by making their lives sweet, and even sold their friends. Thanks to their efforts, the country's "unforgettable dreams, epics that made stones cry" appeared. It is impossible not to think, not to know, not to feel this past. When will memory help us, serve for tomorrow? When he wakes up, realizes and feels! Since great poets, writers, generals, statesmen, as well as our moderns known to the whole world flow in our blood, why should we forget our past and present? Especially, no one has the right to forget the tragedies that our country and compatriots went through during the former Shura era. Not the unborn children of "black eyes", but Usman Nasir, who was "covered with blood petals" in the distant Siberian forests, has the right to live, just like you and us. He was not happy either. It's a pity...

Unfortunately, the traitors who came from us, the scorpions that built a nest on the altar killed Usman Nasir, Abdulla Qadiri, Cholpon and Fitrat. Of course, today it is not appropriate for the representatives of the same nation to condemn each other because of the mistakes made by their grandfathers. But this should not be understood as "the past is gone". The poet's wish is that today's and future generations should learn from this past and be ready for a thousand different tests of life tomorrow! Only then will a nation become a nation, a people. Only then will the crowd withdraw from the psyche of people, and real personalities will be formed. The poet died of a heart attack in July 2001 during a creative trip to Ellikkala district of Karakalpakstan. On this day, Uzbek literature lost not only an Uzbek son. Each of his poems was full of great meaning and

enthusiasm combined with patriotism. Muhammad Yusuf was awarded the Order of "Friendship" and the title of "People's Poet of Uzbekistan" in 1998. According to the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 27, 2013 "On the wide celebration of the 60th anniversary of the birth of the national poet of Uzbekistan Muhammad Yusuf" in 2014, eternal artistic evenings and concerts were held in places, the poet's "Election ", the collection "Muhammad Yusuf's contemporaries in memory" was published, documentary films were made about the poet's life and creative activity. Also, in order to perpetuate the poet's name, a statue of him was erected in the avenue of poets in Chilonzor district of Tashkent city. By the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan on October 4, 2019, this statue was included in the national list of immovable property objects of material and cultural heritage and was taken under state protection. Also, in our country, Muhammad Yusuf creative school was opened in Andijan. Young creative students are studying in this creative school. In conclusion, it should be said that creators like Muhammad Yusuf come to the world only once, and they will go down in history with their works.

References

1. Muhammad Yusuf "We will be happy" published by "Nihal" Tashkent 2017
2. An excellent guide to literature publishing house "Regbooks" Tashkent 2020
3. 8th grade literature textbook, publishing house "Gafur Ghulam" Tashkent, 2006.

Study Of Current Problems And Solutions Of Uzbek Theater Art

Nurpo'latova Ozoda Hasan qizi

3rd year student of the State Institute of Art and Culture of Uzbekistan

Abstract: The article reveals the social significance, pedagogical nature and features of national cultural and intangible values in Uzbekistan during the period of independence.

Keywords: Higher dynamic strategies, creative and creative competences, historical and cultural component, emotional reactions, reflection education, students, national cultural heritage, traditional cultural forms, virtual reality, the Third Renaissance,.

The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On approval of the Concept for the development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan for the period up to 2030" dated October 8, 2019 No. UP-5847 lays the foundations for the development of the higher education system for the near future. It is noteworthy that it indicates such tasks as the formation of students' skills of critical thinking, independent search for information and its analysis, as well as the need for further development of activities to strengthen the spiritual and moral content, patriotic education of young people on the basis of respect for national values, humanism and high spiritual ideas, the formation of youth immunity to alien ideas and ideologies in higher education [1-5].

In the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education" in Article 4. - The basic principles in the field of education are defined by the following objectives:

introduction of national and universal values in education and upbringing;

Parents and other legal representatives of students who have not reached the age of majority are obliged to bring up their children in the spirit of humanism, patriotism, diligence, respect for spiritual, national and universal [5].

The policy of our State is aimed at creating conditions for the development of the individual that can contribute in every possible way to the education of a person who is guided by the cultural, spiritual, moral and socially approved values and rules of conduct in society, who knows, preserves and transmits national cultural values to the next generations.

It is impossible to ignore the fact that artificially created virtual reality is now widely represented in the information and communication system (correspondence), mass media (blogs, news and development channels) and products of creative activity (feature and animation films, blogs, social networks, computer games, video lessons, presentations, audio materials and books). The result of this phenomenon is alienation or complete ignorance by young people of the traditional cultural forms of existence of society and culture in its broad sense – material, spiritual and moral, national, world, ethical, artistic, aesthetic, ecological, etc. Virtual reality is saturated with contradictory value systems, biased and sometimes illiterate interpretations of cultural heritage, the promotion of Westernized, pseudo-liberal attitudes and symbols instead of traditional national ones. It is very difficult for a schoolchild or a student who has not yet formed value orientations and does not have the necessary stock of cultural knowledge to understand this flow. As a result, two parallel realities seem to coexist in society: the above-mentioned socio-virtual constructs and the cultural-historical, spiritual, and moral layer, which is of little interest to the younger generation, and virtual reality, which transmits the models and values of mass culture, alternative and often false, but gressive meanings of human activity and its values [6-10].

The Resolution No. PP-3775 "On Additional Measures to Improve the Quality of Education in Higher Education Institutions and Ensure Their Active Participation in the Large-Scale Reforms Implemented in the Country" dated 05.06.2018 also draws attention to the fact that "... At present, when a sharp ideological struggle continues in the world and threats to spirituality are increasing, there are still cases of young people

disregarding national values, falling under the influence of alien ideas, and unknowingly embarking on the path of crime and extremism."

Therefore, "... The country pays special attention to the systematic organization of spiritual and educational work, to increase the effectiveness of measures taken in this direction, to increase the intellectual potential, consciousness, thinking and worldview, to strengthen the ideological immunity and worldview of the population, especially young people, and to educate a harmoniously developed generation in the spirit of patriotism, love and devotion to the people" [3,4].

Therefore, the trend of introducing young people to cultural values, which existed in Uzbekistan before, needs to be strengthened, and dynamic strategies for the active use of cultural heritage need to be developed. In the process of testing and introducing new methods and technologies of work in the education system, of course, the possibilities of information technologies, electronic educational and methodological complexes, and distance learning should be taken into account.

It is impossible not to note the positivity of the great potential of modern forms and means of education and upbringing – their diversity, multi-channel, polysensory impact on the individual. Therefore, it is necessary to strengthen theoretical and practical research of a culturological nature on the organic inclusion of the content and meanings of the national cultural heritage in the educational process of educational institutions at all levels of continuous education, to provide constant methodological assistance to teachers and educators, combining traditional, innovative and information technologies.

Methodological developments to introduce the younger generation to the national cultural heritage should be developed and applied from the perspective of modern tasks of spiritual development of the citizens of Uzbekistan, the main of which is the idea of the "Third Renaissance", the essence of which was revealed by President Shavkat Mirziyoyev at a solemn ceremony dedicated to the 29th anniversary of the independence of the Republic of Uzbekistan [1].

The First Period of the Eastern Renaissance in the Central Asian Region

Muslim Renaissance of the IX-XII centuries. To this period belongs the activity of the great scientists-encyclopedists Muhammad Khwarizmi, Farabi - philosopher, scientist-encyclopedist, astronomer, mathematician, physician of the medieval East, one of the main representatives of Eastern Aristotelianism, called the Second Teacher (after Aristotle); Abu Ali ibn Sina - philosopher, doctor, musician, Abu Bakr Razi, Abu Reyhan Beruni - historian, geographer, philologist, astronomer, mathematician, geodesist, mineralogist, pharmacologist, geologist, etc., Ahmad Fergani - theologian, linguist, physician [8,10].

The great works of the hadith scholar Imam Bukhari are used in madrasahs and Islamic universities as the main textbook for the study of the Sunnah (sacred tradition) about the Prophet Muhammad.

Hakim Termizi made a major contribution to the development of Sufism – in his work "Khatm al-awliya" (The Seal of the Saints) he developed the doctrine of the saints as messengers of God and the Prophet. Burhaniddin Marghani, Abu Mansura Maturidi, Abu Bakra al-Shoshi, Mahmud Zamakhshari and other world-recognized ancestors have significantly enriched the treasury of religious and philosophical thought [6,7].

The second period of the Eastern Renaissance is the Temurid Renaissance in the XIV-XVI centuries. The great empire created by Amir Temur, the patron saint of scientists, writers, architects and craftsmen from different regions of the world, is of great importance. He encouraged science, education, and the professions. The grandson of Amir Temur - Mirzo Ulugbek - a world-famous outstanding mathematician, astronomer, educator and poet, scientist-encyclopedist, founded one of the largest observatories, built a rich library, created Samarkand School of Scientists. His famous life's work, the catalogue of stars "Zij Ulugbek" ("Ziji-Kuragoni"), is of world significance. has become a work for all mankind. He took care of the development of the system of higher education in the country, he built madrasahs in Samarkand, Gijduvan and Bukhara, which became not only conductors of knowledge, but also concentrated a large number of talented scientists [9].

The rich heritage of thinkers who have contributed to philosophy, exact and natural sciences, history, poetry and literature plays an important role not only in the spiritual development of our region, but also in the history of science and culture of world civilization.

The comprehension of the national cultural heritage by the younger generation is based, first of all, on its cognition in the process of education, when the following is formed:

- readiness of students to actively study the history, customs and traditions of their people, the Uzbek language as the state language, as the cultural code of the nation,

• methods of mastering specific forms of cognition in a tolerant and respectful attitude to the language, history, traditions, customs, religion, cultural artifacts of the national culture of all peoples living on the territory of Uzbekistan;

- Ability to engage in inter-ethnic, inter-confessional and inter-cultural dialogue in order to search for different cultural meanings.

The introduction of the younger generation to the national heritage consists in the formation of a citizen, a patriot who has formed motivational, informational, cognitive, socio-normative, value-based, creative and creative competencies [11-15].

These competencies are formed in the process of acquaintance with the literature of historical and cultural content, museum exhibitions, artifacts, turning to the cultural traditions of one's family, one's life and cultural experience. The task of teachers is to rely on the emotional reactions and experiences of young people, to encourage them to reflect – that is, to analyze the level of their knowledge, the degree of their interest and value attitude to cultural heritage. Purpose of Pedagogical Methods is the awareness of students not only of the importance of studying cultural heritage, but also of the need to constantly improve their lives on its basis in order to pass it on to the next generations.

Literature

1. Speech by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev at the solemn meeting dedicated to the 29th anniversary of the independence of the Republic of Uzbekistan <https://uza.uz/ru/posts/vystuplenie-prezidenta-respubliki-uzbekistan-shavkata-mirziye-31-08-2020>
2. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On approval of the Concept for the development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan for the period up to 2030" dated October 8, 2019 No. UP-5847
3. Boykuziyeva R. "Theoretical and practical issues of researching the characteristics of the formation of social tolerance in students" // Journal of Pedagogical Inventions and Practices. Texas 2023. Б.14-19
4. FarDU Scientific Reports, 2023. No. 3.- B.127-130.
5. Boykuzieva R. "Cultural and Spiritual Potential of the Pedagogical Heritage of Central Asian Encyclopedias as an Important Factor in the Formation of Students' Cognitive Activity" UzMU Khabarlari - Tashkent, No. 1/6.- 2023. P. 53-55.
6. Бойкузиева Р "Cultural and spiritual potential of the pedagogical heritage of scientists-encyclopedists of central Asia" //Иновации в науку: конференция Суми- Украина. 2023 – Б. 160-163.
7. Boykuziyeva R. "Formation of students' knowledge activity on the basis of national cultural heritage" // Web of Humanites: Journal of Social Science and Humanitarian Research. Barselona Ispaniya. 2023. 07. Б. 18-20
8. Mirzayev A. IBN ARABI'S CONCEPT OF VAHDAT UL-VUJUD IN THE VIEW OF THE TRANSLATION OF THE LAW. – 2023. – No. 4. – С. 97-97.
9. Azamovich M. A. The Study of the Ethnic History of the Peoples of the Ferghana Valley at the Beginning of the 19th-20th Centuries //Zien Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities. – 2023. – Т. 17. – С. 34-37.
10. Tishabayeva L.et al. SHAHS MASALASINING YURITILISIYEV // Yosh Direkti Yeriliyeva – 2023. - Т. 2. – №. 1. - S. 26-33.
11. Azamovich M. A. Religious Tolerance Tourism and Jahan Experience //Central Asian Journal of Theoretical and Applied Science. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 9. – С. 93-97.
12. Дилдора Қ. и др. Абдулла қодирий асарларида шахс масаласининг ёритилиши //Yosh Tadqiqotchi Jurnal. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 5. – С. 204-210.
13. Мирзаев А., Махмудова А. Ички туризм истиқболлари //Yosh Tadqiqotchi Jurnal. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 4. – С. 255-262.

-
14. Abdumannonovich N. M. Et al. Uzbekistan's efforts to trace the political situation in Afghanistan /Young Researcher Journal. – 2022. – T. 1. – No. 2. – C. 69-74.
 15. Mirzaev A. A. Geograficheskiy obzor turistichekikh vystavki v uzbekistane [Geographical review of tourist exhibitions in uzbekistan]. – 2022. – №. 2 (74). P. 51-58.